

1 **TITLE**

2 Calcium influx mediated by a mechano-gated ion channel TRPV4 controls actin architecture
3 in lamellipodia to promote cell migration.

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18 **SUMMARY (150 words)**

19 Cell migration is crucial for various physiological processes, enabling cells to navigate
20 through complex environments during development and immune surveillance.

21 Dysregulated cell migration leads to severe pathologies, highlighting the necessity to
22 understand its regulation. Although Ca²⁺ signaling has long been recognized to regulate cell
23 migration, its specific role in coordinating cell protrusion, often the first event of migration,
24 remains elusive. Here, we identify a Ca²⁺ signaling axis involving the mechano-gated
25 channel TRPV4, which regulates lamellipodia protrusions across various cell types. Using
26 Ca²⁺ and FRET imaging, we demonstrate that TRPV4-mediated Ca²⁺ influx is essential for
27 local activation of RhoA, which densifies lamellipodial F-actin through formins.

28 Mechanistically, we identify CaMKII and TEM4 as key mediators relaying the Ca²⁺ signal

29 from TRPV4 to RhoA. This localized Ca²⁺ signaling axis, comprising TRPV4, CaMKII, TEM4,
30 and RhoA, is essential for organizing the actin machinery and promoting cell migration in
31 diverse biological contexts.

32 **KEYWORDS**

33 Cell migration, Actin cytoskeleton, Ca²⁺ signaling, RhoA, Lamelliopodia, TRPV4, CaMKII, Cell
34 protrusion, TEM4, Arhgef17

35 INTRODUCTION

36 Cell migration underlies a diverse array of physiological processes, ranging from
37 embryonic development to adult immune surveillance. When cell migration is mis-
38 regulated, devastating pathological conditions often arise, such as craniofacial
39 malformation¹, chronic wounds², and immunodeficiencies³.

40 Over the past decades, significant progress has been made in understanding the
41 complex mechanisms that govern cell migration. To date, we know that cells use various
42 subcellular compartments to facilitate and coordinate cell movement⁴. At the leading edge
43 of a migrating cell, dynamic membrane protrusions are generated in the direction of
44 movement to propel cell forward. In mesenchymal cells, such as fibroblast and metastatic
45 cancer cells, the membrane protrusions include filopodia (spike-like) and lamellipodia
46 (broad and sheet-like)⁵. While filopodia can drive cell migration in the absence of
47 lamellipodia^{6,7}, lamellipodia are the primary machinery that enables rapid migration
48 through complex biological microenvironments⁷⁻¹⁰. Disruption of signaling pathways
49 essential for lamellipodial protrusions significantly impedes cell migration *in vivo*^{11,12}.

50 Lamellipodia are formed by the polymerization of globular actin (G-actin) into
51 filamentous actin (F-actin) with the aid of the Arp2/3 complex and formins^{13,14}. The
52 polymerizing actin filaments elongate and push against the plasma membrane, providing
53 the biophysical basis of membrane protrusions^{15,16}. For efficient cell movement, the
54 dynamics of the polymerizing actin filaments must be spatially and temporally coordinated
55 and regulated by biochemical signaling¹⁷.

56 The regulation of actin polymerization in lamellipodia has been largely attributed to
57 Rho-family small GTPases, including RhoA, Rac1, and Cdc42, which play a central role in
58 coordinating the spatiotemporal dynamics of the actin cytoskeleton in migrating cells¹⁸⁻²¹.
59 These small GTPases are considered a major convergence point of many migration-related
60 signaling molecules, such as phosphoinositides and receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs)²², for
61 their ability to transduce multiple upstream signals to nucleation promoting factors (NPFs),
62 including the WAVE complex and Arp2/3²³. Among these small GTPases, Rac1 is canonically
63 considered the main driver of lamellipodia formation for its role in promoting branched
64 actin formation via the Arp2/3 complex^{18,24}. However, RhoA and Cdc42 have also been

65 shown to be active and regulate actin assembly in lamellipodia^{20,25,26}. Using genetically
66 encoded biosensors it was shown that RhoA plays a role in protrusion initiation, whereas
67 Rac1 and Cdc42 are involved in reinforcement of the protrusions after the actions of
68 RhoA^{21,27,28}. It was proposed that RhoA initiates protrusions by activating actin
69 polymerization promoting proteins, mDia1 and mDia2 (members of the formin family), at
70 the onset of protrusion, followed by Rac/Cdc42 activation of other actin regulators, e.g.,
71 Arp2/3 complex and VASP, for continuous growth of the lamellipodia^{14,21,27}.

72 In addition to small GTPases, calcium (Ca^{2+}) ions have also emerged as a potent
73 regulator of cell migration. Numerous studies have shown that Ca^{2+} signaling is implicated
74 in all aspects of cell migration, from the formation of protrusions, adhesions to cell
75 detachment²⁹⁻³¹. One of the prominent effectors of Ca^{2+} signaling is myosin II, a molecular
76 motor governing the retraction of lamellipodia and facilitating the attachment of cell
77 protrusions to the extracellular matrix (ECM)³²⁻³⁴. Several studies have also indicated the
78 importance of Ca^{2+} signaling in regulation of actin dynamics at the cell leading edge and
79 protrusive activity of lamellipodia^{35,36}, but unlike the regulation of myosin II by Ca^{2+} which
80 had been described extensively, the regulation of lamellipodia protrusions by Ca^{2+} remains
81 unclear. Specifically, what molecular player control Ca^{2+} signaling at the leading edge and
82 transduce local changes in intracellular Ca^{2+} into the dynamics of lamellipodia actin
83 network, remain unknown.

84 Here, we uncovered a signaling axis that controls the organization of lamellipodial
85 actin network and protrusive activity of migrating cells. To elucidate the molecular basis of
86 lamellipodia regulation by Ca^{2+} signaling, we sought to identify the primary source of Ca^{2+}
87 that contributes to lamellipodia protrusion. By screening a panel of Ca^{2+} -perturbing drugs
88 and subsequently, TRP channels with cell spreading assay, we found that the channel
89 activity of TRPV4, a mechano-gated channel, is critical for lamellipodia protrusions across
90 different cell types. Ratiometric Ca^{2+} imaging demonstrated that suppression of TRPV4
91 disrupts Ca^{2+} influx in lamellipodia without perturbing the Ca^{2+} homeostasis in the cell
92 body. We further demonstrate that suppression of TRPV4 decreases the activity of RhoA in
93 lamellipodia and thereby reducing the density of F-actin in lamellipodia. By using a
94 combination of optogenetic perturbation, FRET imaging, and phospho-proteomic analysis,

95 we identified two key molecular players — CaMKII (calcium/calmodulin-dependent
96 protein kinase II) and its phosphorylation target, Tumour Endothelial Marker 4 (TEM4) —
97 that transduce the Ca²⁺ signal from TRPV4 to RhoA. This Ca²⁺ signaling axis is essential for
98 lamellipodia protrusions and cell migration in different biological contexts. Together, our
99 findings reveal a conserved, local Ca²⁺ signaling axis composed of TRPV4, CaMKII, TEM4,
100 and RhoA, that finetunes the actin machinery at the cell leading edge during cell migration.

101 **RESULTS**

102 **Ca²⁺ influx through a mechanogated channel TRPV4 facilitates lamellipodia** 103 **protrusion**

104 To investigate the role of Ca²⁺ signaling in the regulation of lamellipodia protrusion,
105 we examined the intracellular Ca²⁺ dynamics of mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs)
106 undergoing cell spreading, a process primarily driven by Arp2/3-containing lamellipodial
107 actin networks (Figure S1A)^{37,38}. MEFs were transfected with a construct encoding the Ca²⁺
108 biosensor GCaMP6f and soluble mCherry, separated by a T2A self-cleavage peptide,
109 allowing near-equimolar expression of both proteins from a single mRNA transcript³⁹.
110 Twenty-four hours post transfection, the cells were allowed to spread on fibronectin (FN)-
111 coated coverslips, and their spreading kinetics and Ca²⁺ patterns were visualized by time-
112 lapse confocal microscopy. To determine the relative local concentration of intracellular
113 Ca²⁺, a ratiometric GCaMP6f signal was calculated by dividing the GCaMP6f intensity by the
114 intensity of mCherry (hereafter referred to as the GCaMP signal). These experiments
115 revealed a pronounced gradient of GCaMP signal across the cells that persisted throughout
116 the entire duration of spreading and peaked at the protruding cell edge (Figure 1A).
117 Furthermore, the local GCaMP signal intensity positively correlated with cell edge speed
118 (Figure 1B), suggesting a functional link between Ca²⁺ signaling at the lamellipodia and its
119 protrusive activity. Consistent with these findings, depletion of intracellular Ca²⁺ using
120 BAPTA-AM abolished the GCaMP signal gradient and reduced cell spreading speed (Figures
121 1C-E and S1B). Conversely, cells treated with the Ca²⁺ ionophore ionomycin exhibited a
122 rapid increase in GCaMP signal at the protruding cell edge, which coincided with a faster

123 cell spreading (Figures S1C-E). Together, these data demonstrate an association between
124 the local level of Ca^{2+} at the lamellipodia and cell protrusion.

125 The concentration of cytoplasmic Ca^{2+} is controlled by the influx of extracellular Ca^{2+}
126 as well as the efflux of intracellular Ca^{2+} ⁴⁰⁻⁴². Despite being the primary storage site for
127 intracellular Ca^{2+} , the endoplasmic reticulum is mainly absent from the cell periphery^{43,44}
128 and is therefore unlikely to be involved in the regulation of local Ca^{2+} level in lamellipodia.
129 Consistent with this, cells treated with thapsigargin, an inhibitor of sarco-endoplasmic
130 reticulum ATPases, displayed no changes in GCaMP signal gradient and cell spreading speed
131 compared to control cells (Figures 1D, E and S1F). Therefore, we focused on the
132 contribution of extracellular Ca^{2+} to lamellipodia protrusion. We found that chelation of
133 extracellular Ca^{2+} or suppression of stretch-activated channels on the plasma membrane
134 with GdCl_3 significantly reduced cell spreading speed (Figures 1D and E), suggesting that
135 influx of extracellular Ca^{2+} through stretch-activated channels is primarily responsible for
136 the control of lamellipodia protrusion.

137 We next conducted short interfering RNA (siRNA) knockdown experiments targeting
138 Ca^{2+} -permeable transient receptor potential (TRP) channels, a superfamily of cation
139 channels activable by mechanical forces^{45,46}. We altered the expression of 18 TRP channels,
140 expressed by fibroblasts (Figure S1G), by using siRNAs and measured cell spreading speed
141 as described above. Depletion of four channels (TRPV1, TRPV4, TRPV5 and TRPV6) was
142 found to suppress lamellipodia protrusion in spreading cells with TRPV4 having the
143 strongest effect (Figures 1F and G).

144 Previous work has shown that TRPV4 controls cell-ECM attachment by modulating
145 $\beta 1$ integrin expression⁴⁷. To examine whether the effect of TRPV4 on lamellipodia is
146 mediated by integrin-based adhesion complexes, we assessed spreading kinetics of control
147 and TRPV4-depleted cells on poly-L-lysine, the substrate that permits integrin-independent
148 adhesion⁴⁸. These experiments revealed that the reduction in lamellipodia protrusion due
149 to TRPV4 depletion was not influenced by integrin-based adhesion, as evidenced by slower
150 spreading of TRPV4-depleted cells on poly-L-lysine (Figures S1H and I).

151 To test the role of extracellular Ca^{2+} influx through TRPV4, we pharmacologically
152 suppressed the channel with HC-067047, a selective TRPV4 inhibitor that alters channel
153 permeability by creating a hydrophobic seal in the pore⁴⁹. Cells treated with 10 μM HC-
154 067047 exhibited a significant reduction in the rate of cell spreading (Figures 1F and G).
155 Such changes were conserved amongst various cell types, as U2OS, HeLa, and MDA-MB-231
156 cells all displayed a significant decrease in cell spreading speed upon TRPV4 inhibition
157 (Figures S2A-C). Collectively, these data demonstrate a key role for TRPV4-mediated Ca^{2+}
158 influx in cell spreading and suggest TRPV4 involvement in the control of lamellipodia
159 protrusion.

160 The changes in cell spreading speed prompted us to examine the role of TRPV4 in
161 lamellipodia protrusion in polarized fibroblasts. Using immunofluorescence (IF)
162 microscopy, we mapped actin and the ArpC2 subunit of the Arp2/3 complex (which is a
163 lamellipodial protein required for the protrusion) in control and TRPV4-suppressed MEFs.
164 Among four TRPV4-specific siRNAs, two were found to suppress TRPV4 expression
165 efficiently (Figures S2D-F). The suppression of TRPV4 with siRNAs or HC-067047
166 significantly decreased the average length of lamellipodia, resulting in $\approx 40\%$ reduction in
167 the fraction of cell edge positive for ArpC2 (Figures S2G and H). These data indicate that,
168 while not being essential, TRPV4 potentiates lamellipodia formation. Next, we investigated
169 the dynamic behavior of lamellipodia using live-cell differential interference contrast
170 imaging. Consistent with our findings with spreading cells, suppression of TRPV4 led to a
171 $\approx 25\%$ reduction in protrusion speed in polarized migrating MEFs, and this effect was fully
172 rescued upon overexpression of siRNA-resistant TRPV4 (Figures 1H and I; Video S1).
173 Collectively, these data identify the mechano-gated Ca^{2+} -permeable channel TRPV4 as a key
174 component of a Ca^{2+} -dependent signaling pathway regulating protrusion of lamellipodia.

175 **Local regulation of Ca^{2+} via TRPV4 drives lamellipodia protrusion**

176 To further investigate the role of the TRPV4 channel in the control of Ca^{2+} - and
177 protrusive dynamics, we first visualized TRPV4 and filamentous actin (F-actin) by IF
178 microscopy. Similar to other mechano-gated ion channels⁵⁰, TRPV4 exhibited a uniform
179 distribution across the plasma membrane with a notable portion of TRPV4 localized at

180 lamellipodia (Figure S2I). Inspired by this localization, we next tested whether TRPV4
181 controls the local Ca^{2+} concentration in lamellipodia. We dynamically mapped the Ca^{2+}
182 biosensor GCaMP6f, soluble mCherry, and Ftractin-emiRFP670 in both control and TRPV4-
183 inhibited MEFs (Figure 2A). Ratiometric imaging revealed a significantly higher GCaMP
184 signal in the protruding cell edge of control cells. However, upon TRPV4 inhibition, the
185 lamellipodial GCaMP signal reduced by $\approx 20\%$ within a matter of seconds (Figures 2B-D;
186 Video S2). The suppression of TRPV4 had a negligible effect on the GCaMP signal calculated
187 for the whole cell (Figures 2A and B), suggesting that TRPV4 serves as a local regulator of
188 Ca^{2+} influx in lamellipodia.

189 Lamellipodia are highly dynamic cellular structures exhibiting rapid cycles of
190 protrusion and retraction⁵¹; therefore, we tested whether the TRPV4 channel is
191 differentially activated during any distinct phase of the cycle. To test this, we compared the
192 GCaMP signal intensity in protruding, stalling, and retracting lamellipodia of control and
193 TRPV4-inhibited cells (Figures 2D-F). These experiments revealed that in control cells, the
194 Ca^{2+} level was highest in actively protruding lamellipodia, while transitioning to stalling and
195 retracting states coincided with $\approx 15\%$ decrease in GCaMP signal intensity. In contrast, the
196 suppression of TRPV4 abolished the pattern of Ca^{2+} influx during the protrusion-retraction
197 cycle, indicating a tight coupling between TRPV4 activation and the protrusion phase of
198 lamellipodia. These findings were further corroborated by a cross-correlation analysis,
199 which revealed a strong positive correlation between Ca^{2+} influx and the onset of
200 lamellipodia protrusion in control, but not TRPV4-inhibited cells (Figure 2G). The acute
201 suppression of TRPV4 with HC-067047 stopped the extension of lamellipodia, causing them
202 to stall or collapse (Figure 2D), indicating a key role for TRPV4-mediated Ca^{2+} influx in
203 lamellipodia protrusion.

204 Next, we sought to examine the effects of an increase in Ca^{2+} influx via TRPV4 on
205 cellular protrusions. We treated MEFs with a TRPV4 agonist (GSK1016790A) and
206 quantified the fraction of the cell edge that was positive for the lamellipodia marker
207 cortactin (Figure 2H). Ectopic activation of TRPV4 nearly doubled the amount of
208 lamellipodia in fibroblasts. Interestingly, this effect was not specific to the activation of

209 TRPV4 as indicated by a similar effect of Ca^{2+} ionophore, ionomycin, on protrusions
210 (Figures 2H and I). To test whether a local increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} is sufficient to
211 induce lamellipodia protrusion directly, we examined the effects of Ca^{2+} uncaging from the
212 photolabile Ca^{2+} chelator NP-EGTA-AM on the dynamics of the stalling cell edge. Localized
213 uncaging was induced by illuminating a small ($3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}$) region of the cytoplasm directly
214 adjacent to the stalling cell edge with a low-intensity 405 nm laser. This treatment, while
215 having no noticeable effect on control cells, resulted in a $\approx 20\%$ increase in GCaMP signal in
216 the vicinity of the illuminated area in NP-EGTA-AM-loaded cells (Figure 2J). Notably, the
217 magnitude of uncaging was quantitatively similar to the Ca^{2+} influx mediated by TRPV4
218 (Figure 2B). The light-stimulated Ca^{2+} uncaging triggered the protrusion of the stalling cell
219 edge, with over 80% of the tested cells exhibiting robust protrusion (Figures 2K and L;
220 Video S3), demonstrating that a local increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} is sufficient to induce
221 lamellipodia protrusion. Together, these results indicate that TRPV4 facilitates lamellipodia
222 protrusion through the local control of Ca^{2+} influx.

223 **TRPV4-mediated Ca^{2+} influx modulates cell edge protrusions through the regulation** 224 **of F-actin density in lamellipodia**

225 Previous studies have shown that Ca^{2+} influxes exert control over lamellipodia
226 protrusion by triggering myosin activation at distant locations, *i.e.*, within the lamellae,
227 resulting in a partial retraction of the nearby protruding lamellipodia³². Therefore, we
228 examined whether the modulation of lamellipodia protrusion by TRPV4 is contingent upon
229 myosin activation. Initially, we utilized IF microscopy to visualize the distribution of the
230 phosphoserine-19 myosin regulatory light chain-2 (pS19MLC2) in control and TRPV4-
231 inhibited cells. Consistent with previous reports^{52,53}, these experiments revealed a
232 monotonic gradient of pS19MLC2 intensity, with minimal amounts of pS19MLC2 near the
233 cell edge (Figures S3A and B). This distribution of pS19MLC2 was unaffected by TRPV4
234 inhibition, indicating that myosin activity is not governed by TRPV4-mediated Ca^{2+} influx.

235 To directly assess the role of myosin contractility in the regulation of lamellipodia
236 protrusion by TRPV4, we examined the effect of TRPV4 inhibition on cells in which myosin
237 was suppressed by blebbistatin (Figures S3C and D). This experiment revealed that

238 suppression of myosin had a minimal effect on the cellular response to TRPV4 inhibition, as
239 the suppression of TRPV4 continued to inhibit lamellipodia protrusion. Collectively, these
240 findings demonstrate that the control of lamellipodia protrusion by TRPV4 is independent
241 of distant changes in myosin contractility, and instead strongly suggest a local Ca^{2+} -
242 dependent regulation of the lamellipodial actin network.

243 We next analyzed the role of TRPV4 in actin organization in lamellipodia. By using IF
244 microscopy, we visualized F-actin and cortactin in control and TRPV4-suppressed cells. We
245 found a significant decrease in lamellipodial actin intensity, with a reduction of 47% in
246 TRPV4-depleted cells and 34% in TRPV4-inhibited cells compared to their respective
247 controls (Figures 3A and B). This marked decline in lamellipodial F-actin coincided with a
248 $\approx 40\%$ decrease in the intensity of the actin nucleating factor Arp2/3 and the intensity of
249 cortactin (Figures 3A and C-E). Notably, the recruitment of Abi1, an essential component of
250 the WAVE complex and an upstream regulator of Arp2/3⁵⁴, to lamellipodia was unaffected
251 by TRPV4 inhibition, suggesting that Arp2/3 activity is preserved upon TRPV4 inhibition.
252 Nevertheless, the reduced actin and Arp2/3 staining strongly indicates that suppression of
253 TRPV4 perturbs the organization of the actin network in lamellipodia.

254 To directly test this hypothesis, we examined F-actin density in cells treated with
255 either DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor by using platinum replica electron microscopy (PREM).
256 The PREM images did not reveal any gross differences in the organization of actin network
257 in lamellipodia of control and TRPV4-inhibited cells. Nevertheless, the quantitative analysis
258 of the PREM images revealed $\approx 60\%$ increase in the sample area that lacks platinum coating,
259 indicating a significant decrease in F-actin density in lamellipodia. Collectively, these
260 findings suggest that TRPV4 facilitates the assembly of the dense network of lamellipodial
261 actin.

262 **TRPV4 upregulates lamellipodia F-actin density through the RhoA/formin signaling** 263 **module**

264 We next sought to dissect the molecular mechanism through which TRPV4 regulates
265 the density of F-actin in lamellipodia. Given that the control of actin polymerization is
266 primarily orchestrated by the Rho-family small GTPases - RhoA, Rac1, and Cdc42 - we

267 hypothesized that TRPV4 facilitates the assembly of lamellipodial F-actin by activating one
268 or more of these small GTPases. To test this, we examined the effect of TRPV4 suppression
269 on the spatiotemporal pattern of RhoA, Rac1, and Cdc42 by using Förster Resonance
270 Energy Transfer (FRET) biosensors. The biosensors were validated by measuring the FRET
271 efficiency of the dominant-negative (RhoA^{T19N}, Rac1^{T17N}, and Cdc42^{T17N}) and constitutively
272 active (RhoA^{Q63L}, Rac1^{Q61L}, and Cdc42^{Q61L}) mutants (Figures S4A-E). In agreement with
273 previous reports^{18,19,21}, FRET imaging revealed a broad gradient of Rac1 and Cdc42 activity
274 across the protruding edges of control cells with the highest activity localized at the tip of
275 the cell edge (Figures S4B and C). Notably, neither the integrated FRET efficiency (FRET_{eff})
276 signal nor the distribution of Rac1 and Cdc42 FRET intensity across the cell edge were
277 significantly affected by the suppression of TRPV4. In agreement with these data, activity-
278 based Rac1- and Cdc42-GTP pull-down assays did not reveal a significant change in the
279 average cellular activity of Rac1 and Cdc42 upon TRPV4 inhibition (Figures S4F-G).
280 Together, these data demonstrate that TRPV4 is unlikely to regulate lamellipodial actin
281 through the modulation of Rac1 and Cdc42 activity.

282 Previous studies have demonstrated the activation of RhoA at the distal tip of a
283 protruding lamellipodia and established that it plays a role in the assembly of actin
284 filaments that are competent for Arp2/3 binding^{21,27,28}. Hence, we initially assessed RhoA
285 activity in control and TRPV4-inhibited cells using an affinity-based pull-down assay. We
286 found that suppression of TRPV4 had a minimal impact on the overall cellular activity of
287 RhoA (Figure 4A), mirroring the unchanged myosin contractility upon TRPV4 inhibition
288 (Figures S3A-B). To determine if the spatial pattern of RhoA activity is altered upon TRPV4
289 suppression, we compared the distribution of active RhoA, visualized by a FRET biosensor,
290 in control and TRPV4-inhibited cells. Consistent with previous reports^{21,55}, RhoA activity
291 exhibited a peak at the tips of control cell protruding edges and gradually decreased
292 towards the cell body (Figures 4B-D). However, TRPV4-inhibited cells exhibited a distinct
293 spatial pattern of RhoA activity, despite maintaining a comparable overall activity level
294 (Figures 4B-E). Notably, in TRPV4-inhibited cells, active RhoA was no longer enriched in the
295 lamellipodia, as evidenced by a flattened intensity profile and a reduced lamellipodia-to-cell

296 body FRET_{eff} ratio (Figures 4D and F), suggesting that TRPV4-mediated Ca²⁺ influx activates
297 RhoA at protruding cell edges.

298 Next, we sought to determine whether the activation of RhoA/formin(s) signaling
299 module, which initiates actin polymerization at the onset of protrusion and subsequently
300 reinforces the lamellipodia network^{21,27,28}, is sufficient to explain the effect of TRPV4
301 inhibition on the actin density in lamellipodia. To test this, we examined actin density in
302 cells treated with TRPV4 or RhoA inhibitors (C3 transferase) and immunostained with
303 cortactin antibody and phalloidin. In agreement with previous reports^{56,57}, cells treated
304 with C3 transferase exhibited a significant reduction in the number and intensity of stress
305 fibers (Figures 4 H), indicating a decline in Rho-mediated myosin contractility. Conversely,
306 TRPV4 inhibition had a minimal effect on stress fibers, in line with our finding of no
307 significant change in the overall cellular RhoA activity upon TRPV4 inhibition. However,
308 cells treated with either TRPV4 inhibitor or C3 transferase exhibited a comparable (~40%)
309 decrease in the intensity of the lamellipodia network, supporting the notion of TRPV4- and
310 RhoA-dependent regulation of actin in lamellipodia. Furthermore, suppression of the
311 downstream RhoA effectors, formins, partially recapitulated the phenotype of TRPV4
312 inhibited cells as evident from the 20% decrease in lamellipodia actin density. Co-inhibition
313 of formins and TRPV4 did not additively decrease actin density, suggesting that
314 lamellipodia actin is controlled through the TRPV4-dependent activation of the
315 RhoA/formin(s) signaling module, rather than by the convergence of these pathways on
316 actin regulation. Together, these data identify a new signaling modules composed of
317 TRPV4/RhoA/formins that control the organization of lamellipodia actin network.

318 **CaMKII facilitates lamellipodia protrusion and upregulates RhoA activity in a TRPV4-** 319 **dependent manner**

320 We next sought to examine whether the control of lamellipodia architecture and
321 protrusion dynamics by TRPV4 is mediated by calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein
322 kinase II (CaMKII), which is known to remodel the actin cytoskeleton through small
323 GTPases in neuronal spines⁵⁸. In non-neuronal cells, including vascular smooth muscle cells
324 and cancer cells, CaMKII has been implicated in migration and invasion⁵⁹⁻⁶¹.

325 We first examined the level of active CaMKII (pCaMKII^{T286}) in control and TRPV4-
326 inhibited cells by using western blotting and immunostaining with a phospho-specific
327 antibody. Inhibiting TRPV4, much like its effect on intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration, did not
328 alter overall CaMKII activity, as indicated by similar pCaMKII intensities in lysates of control
329 and TRPV4-inhibited cells (Figure S5A). However, IF microscopy revealed a significantly
330 lower level of pCaMKII in the lamellipodia of TRPV4-inhibited cells, accompanied by
331 reduced F-actin intensity (Figures 5A-C). Moreover, quantitative analysis revealed a strong
332 positive correlation between local CaMKII activity and actin density in lamellipodia (Figure
333 5C), suggesting that CaMKII is involved in the regulation of the lamellipodial actin network.

334 Next, we sought to determine whether actin density in lamellipodia is regulated by
335 CaMKII downstream of TRPV4. To test this, we compared the intensities of phalloidin-
336 stained actin in lamellipodia of cells treated with CaMKII or TRPV4 inhibitors. We found
337 that suppression of CaMKII with 10 μ M KN-93 reduced F-actin intensity by 42%,
338 phenocopying the effect of TRPV4 inhibition (Figures 5D and E). Furthermore, the effect of
339 TRPV4 inhibitor was fully rescued by ectopic activation of CaMKII, as evidenced by a
340 significant increase in lamellipodial actin intensity in TRPV4-inhibited cells expressing a
341 constitutively active CaMKII mutant (CaMKII α ^{T286D})⁶¹, compared to the cells expressing
342 wild-type CaMKII (Figures 5F and G). Collectively, these data strongly suggest that CaMKII
343 acts as a downstream effector of TRPV4 enabling Ca²⁺-dependent regulation of the density
344 of F-actin in lamellipodia.

345 To determine whether CaMKII regulates RhoA, we assessed the effect of CaMKII
346 inhibition with 10 μ M KN-93 on the activity of RhoA by using FRET biosensor. We found
347 that CaMKII suppression led to a modest (\approx 20%) decrease in RhoA activity throughout the
348 cell (Figure 5H). Local mapping of RhoA activity also showed a reduced RhoA activity in
349 protrusions (Figures 5I and J).

350 To assess the functional role of CaMKII activation downstream of TRPV4 in
351 lamellipodia protrusions, we employed an optogenetic inhibitor of CaMKII (paAIP2)⁶².
352 Local suppression of CaMKII activity in protruding lamellipodia of MEFs using 405 nm laser
353 stimulation resulted in rapid protrusion cessation within a few seconds (Figures 5K and L;

354 Video S4). Quantification of the protrusion response upon local CaMKII inhibition showed
355 that over 60% of cells switched from protruding to stalling or retracting (Figure 2K). Such
356 an effect has not been observed upon paAIP2 activation in cells pre-treated with TRPV4
357 inhibition, indicating that the regulation of lamellipodia protrusion by CaMKII depends
358 strongly on TRPV4-mediated Ca²⁺ influx. Together, these data demonstrate that CaMKII
359 activity is required for enabling the control of lamellipodial architecture and protrusion by
360 TRPV4.

361 **TEM4, a RhoGEF, links local activity of TRPV4/CaMKII signaling module to RhoA** 362 **regulation**

363 The regulation of protrusion and lamellipodial RhoA activity by CaMKII suggests a
364 potential activation of RhoA through CaMKII-mediated phosphorylation. However, the
365 known phosphorylation sites on RhoA, Ser26 or Ser188, have previously been reported to
366 inactivate RhoA upon phosphorylation^{63,64}, making it unlikely that CaMKII activates RhoA
367 via direct phosphorylation. Therefore, we reasoned that TRPV4 may regulate RhoA activity
368 in lamellipodia through CaMKII-dependent phosphorylation of Rho GTPase regulators. To
369 identify regulators of RhoA phosphorylated in a CaMKII/TRPV4 dependent manner, we
370 conducted phosphoproteomic profiling of cellular protrusions. To improve the sensitivity of
371 the assay for low abundance proteins, we biochemically isolated the protrusion fractions as
372 described previously^{65,66}. MEFs cultured on FN-coated polycarbonate membranes with 3
373 μm pores were exposed to a gradient of chemoattractant (1—10% FBS), which induces
374 protrusions extending through the pores (Figure 6A). This treatment effectively triggered
375 protrusions while restricting cell body translocation as evidenced by the positive F-actin
376 staining on both the upper and lower surface of the membrane, and DAPI staining
377 restricted to the upper surface (Figure 6B). The purity of the isolated protrusion fraction
378 was further confirmed by western blotting for vasodilator-stimulated phosphoprotein
379 (VASP), a molecular marker of protrusions⁶⁷. The isolated fractions of cellular protrusions
380 exhibited a significant enrichment with VASP compared to the fraction of cell body (Figure
381 S6A).

382 To identify the molecular players involved in the regulation of RhoA by the
383 TRPV4/CaMKII signaling pathway, we performed a phosphoproteomic analysis of
384 lamellipodia fractions isolated from the control, TRPV4-inhibited, and CaMKII-inhibited
385 cells (Figure 6C). We calculated median MS intensities of three biological replicates for each
386 condition and identified 1447 phosphopeptides with reduced phosphorylation level in both
387 the TRPV4 and CaMKII lamellipodia fractions. Following bioinformatic analysis, six RhoA
388 regulators were identified. We then used siRNA to deplete each candidate protein and
389 evaluated lamellipodia protrusive activity in a cell spreading assay (Figure 6D). Depletion of
390 Arhgef2 (Guanine Exchange Factor H1, GEF-H1) and Arhgef17 (Tumour Endothelial Marker
391 4, TEM4) resulted in a reduced lamellipodia protrusion speed similar to that seen with
392 TRPV4 inhibition.

393 Previous studies have shown that GEF-H1 can regulate cellular protrusions by
394 promoting focal adhesion turnover^{68,69}. However, our experiments demonstrated an
395 integrin-independent role of TRPV4 in regulating protrusion dynamics (Figures S1H and I),
396 suggesting that GEF-H1 is unlikely to mediate TRPV4's effects on lamellipodia. This was
397 further supported by the negligible impact of GEF-H1 depletion on lamellipodia actin
398 density (Figure S6B). Together these data make it unlikely that TRPV4-mediated Ca²⁺ influx
399 promotes lamellipodial protrusion via GEF-H1 and leave TEM4 as the most plausible
400 candidate to link TRPV4/CaMKII activity to RhoA.

401 To examine the role of TEM4 in the regulation of lamellipodia protrusions, we
402 depleted TEM4 by using smart pool siRNAs and investigated the dynamic behavior of
403 lamellipodia using live cell imaging. Consistent with our findings on spreading cells,
404 depletion of TEM4 led to a $\approx 20\%$ reduction in protrusion speed in polarized MEFs (Figure
405 6E). Next, we compared the pattern of RhoA activity visualized with the FRET biosensor in
406 control and TEM4-depleted cells. This analysis revealed only a minimal, not statistically
407 significant change in the overall RhoA activity upon TEM4 depletion (Figures 6F and G).
408 However, TEM4-depleted cells exhibited an altered spatial pattern of RhoA activity
409 characterized by a lower level of active RhoA in lamellipodia compared to the control cells
410 (Figure 6H). Similar to the effect of TRPV4 inhibitor, depletion of TEM4 efficiently abolished

411 the enrichment of active RhoA at the protruding cell edge as evident from a lamellipodia-to-
412 cell-body RhoA activity ratio of one (Figures 6F and H). TEM4 depletion also phenocopied
413 the effect of TRPV4 inhibition on the organization of the actin cytoskeleton. While depletion
414 of TEM4 did not affect contractile cytoskeletal structures, e.g., stress fibers and actin arches,
415 it markedly decreased the density of the lamellipodia actin network (Figures 6I and J).
416 Inhibiting TRPV4 in TEM4-depleted cells did not additively decrease lamellipodial actin
417 density, suggesting the control of TEM4 activity downstream of TRPV4. Together, these data
418 identify TEM4 as a key component of the TRPV4/CaMKII signaling axis providing the
419 control of lamellipodia actin network through local activation of RhoA.

420 **The TRPV4 signaling axis facilitates cell protrusion and cell migration in vitro and in** 421 **vivo**

422 To determine the physiological significance of the signaling events triggered by
423 TRPV4-mediated Ca²⁺ influx in lamellipodia, we assessed cell migration in vitro and in vivo
424 under the experimental conditions that suppress the key components of
425 TRPV4/CaMKII/TEM4/RhoA signaling axis. Considering the strong effect of RhoA and
426 CaMKII inhibition on cytoskeletal structures and focal adhesions^{70,71}, we focused on cells
427 treated with TRPV4 inhibitor or depleted for TEM4. As shown above (Figures 1H, I and 6I),
428 these treatments efficiently suppressed lamellipodia protrusion, while having minimal if
429 any effect on cell morphology (Figures S7A-D). Automated tracking of individual cells
430 revealed that both TRPV4-inhibited and TEM4-depleted cells migrated markedly slower
431 than control cells (Figures 7A, B, D; Video S5). We also calculated the directionality index
432 (DI = Displacement/Path; Figures 7C) from cell motion tracks, where a higher DI indicates
433 more directionally persistent movement⁷². This analysis showed that suppression of TRPV4
434 had a negligible effect on cell migration directionality (Figure 7E). While depletion of TEM4
435 slightly, but significantly, reduced the directionality of cell migration (Figure 7E), this effect
436 can likely be attributed to a suppression of myosin contractility in the cell lamella, which
437 has been reported previously⁷³.

438 To test whether the effects of TRPV4 suppression on cell migration can be attributed
439 to changes in cell-substrate interactions, we transfected MEFs with paxillin-eGFP, a marker

440 of integrin adhesion complexes, and assessed morphological properties of focal adhesions
441 upon suppression of TRPV4 with 10 μ M HC-067047. These experiments revealed only
442 minor, not statistically significant differences in size and number of focal adhesions
443 (Figures S7E and F), indicating that the suppression of migration is not due to changes in
444 integrin adhesion complexes. Together, these data suggest that the control of lamellipodia
445 protrusion by TRPV4 signaling axis facilitates cell migration.

446 To examine the contribution of the TRPV4 signaling axis in cell migration under
447 physiological conditions, we employed two assays. We first assessed the effect of TRPV4
448 inhibition and TEM4 depletion on cell migration in 3D matrices. For these experiments, we
449 labelled MEFs with Hoechst, which enabled visualization of the cell movement by spinning
450 disk confocal microscopy. We treated these cells with either DMSO, 10 μ M HC-067047, or
451 TEM4-targeting siRNA and embedded them in three-dimensional collagen scaffolds (Figure
452 7F, G). Timelapse imaging of cell movement showed a significant reduction in cell migration
453 upon the suppression of the components of TRPV4 signaling axis (Figure 7H), although
454 these treatments had a minimal effect on overall cell morphology (Figure S7G).

455 Next, we utilized mouse melanoblast migration in a skin explant as a model (Figure
456 7I). Since the migration of melanoblasts is known to rely on lamellipodial protrusion¹¹, we
457 hypothesized that pharmacological inhibition of TRPV4 suppresses lamellipodial
458 protrusion in melanoblasts and consequently impairs their migration. To test this
459 hypothesis, we tracked and quantified the migration of melanoblasts in the absence or
460 presence of TRPV4 inhibitor. Unlike the minimal effect of TRPV4 inhibition on cell
461 morphology in a 2D model (Figures S7A-D), TRPV4 inhibition of melanoblasts in skin
462 explants resulted in a significantly rounder cell morphology compared to the control cells
463 (Figures S7I and J). TRPV4-inhibited melanoblasts exhibited a lower protrusion speed and
464 migrated at a significantly reduced speed compared to the control cells (Figures 7J-N and
465 Figure 7SH and J; Video S6). Collectively, these data underscore the importance of the
466 TRPV4 signaling axis in regulation of cell migration in vitro and in vivo.

467 **DISCUSSION**

468 Our study reports the discovery of a signaling axis that regulates protrusive activity
469 of migrating cells by facilitating the assembly of dense actin network in lamellipodia. By
470 screening a panel of Ca²⁺-perturbing drugs and siRNAs targeting calcium channels in a cell
471 spreading assay, we identified a stretch-activated channel, TRPV4, as a positive regulator of
472 lamellipodia across different cell types. Quantitative imaging revealed that suppression of
473 TRPV4 reduced Ca²⁺ influx in lamellipodia, which subsequently reduces the actin density in
474 lamellipodia and suppresses protrusion. We demonstrated that the coupling between the
475 local concentration of Ca²⁺ in lamellipodia and F-actin density is mediated by a Ca²⁺-
476 dependent kinase CaMKII, which phosphorylates a RhoGEF TEM4 resulting in a local
477 activation of RhoA in lamellipodia. Such activation of RhoA facilitates actin polymerization
478 in a formin-dependent manner. Suppression of this signaling axis
479 (TRPV4/CaMKII/TEM4/RhoA), decreases the protrusive activity. Importantly, we
480 demonstrated the physiological importance of this signaling axis in different biological
481 contexts, including fibroblast migration in vitro and melanoblast migration ex vivo.

482 The role of Ca²⁺ in the regulation of lamellipodial protrusions has been previously
483 studied^{32,41}. The proposed model postulates that Ca²⁺ influx in protrusions activates Ca²⁺-
484 dependent myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) that contracts the actin network and causes
485 retraction. While this model accounts for certain aspects of lamellipodia regulation, it does
486 not align with other findings that demonstrate a positive role of Ca²⁺ in protrusive
487 activity^{30,35,36,74,75}. Such discrepancies suggest that our current model of Ca²⁺ regulation in
488 lamellipodia is not accurate. The previous studies indicated that Ca²⁺ influx in protrusions,
489 which encompass both lamella and lamellipodia, triggers retraction^{32,41}. On the other hand,
490 our data show that a localized Ca²⁺ influx (within 2-3 μm of the cell edge), controlled by
491 TRPV4, facilitates F-actin assembly in lamellipodia and promotes protrusions. An
492 important, but often overlooked, distinction between our study and the previous studies is
493 in the precise location of the Ca²⁺ influx. This study, together with other studies^{32,41}, suggest
494 that contrary to previous beliefs that Ca²⁺ ion is a highly diffusive signaling cue⁷⁶, Ca²⁺
495 signaling can be local and highly compartmentalized. Proximal Ca²⁺ signaling in

496 lamellipodia supports F-actin assembly and facilitates protrusion, while distal Ca²⁺
497 signaling in lamella, which is enriched with myosin-II^{77,78}, causes the MLCK/myosin-II-
498 mediated retraction³². Such revised model of lamellipodia regulation by Ca²⁺ is also more
499 consistent with findings that myosin-II is unlikely to contract lamellipodial F-actin, due to
500 its suppression by tyrosine phosphorylation⁷⁹ and its low abundance in lamellipodia
501 (Figures S3A-B;⁷⁸). Based on the current literature and our results, we hypothesize that
502 such intricate compartmentalization of Ca²⁺ signaling is mediated by the local regulation of
503 stretch-activated channels, plasma membrane Ca²⁺ pumps, such as Ca²⁺-ATPase (PMCA)⁸⁰,
504 ER membrane Ca²⁺ channels⁸¹, and Ca²⁺ buffers^{82,83}. By spatially compartmentalizing a
505 signaling factor, such as the Ca²⁺ ion, the same signaling factor can take on different roles in
506 regulating lamellipodia protrusions. Understanding how Ca²⁺ signaling is spatially and
507 temporally compartmentalized will be an exciting avenue for future studies.

508 Consistent with our findings that TRPV4 regulates lamellipodia protrusions, earlier
509 work has described TRPV4 as lamellipodia-localized in various cell types, including human
510 skin keratinocytes, Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO), and glioblastoma cells^{84,85}. Importantly,
511 our study also reveals that TRPV4 is predominantly active in lamellipodia (Figures 2A-G)
512 and such a local activation of TRPV4 controls the activity of CaMKII (Figures 5A-C), a kinase
513 well-characterized in neurons. In fact, the regulation of CaMKII by TRPV4 has been shown
514 in neurons⁸⁶ but has never been described in other migratory cell types, such as fibroblasts.
515 Therefore, whether such regulation exists in other cell types and what role of TRPV4-
516 dependent CaMKII activity plays in cell migration remained completely unknown. To this
517 end, we first showed that TRPV4 regulates CaMKII activity in lamellipodia of MEFs (Figures
518 4A and B), and further demonstrated the necessity of local CaMKII activity for maintaining
519 cellular protrusive activity and lamellipodial F-actin organization, as shown by the
520 suppression of protrusions upon optogenetic inhibition of CaMKII (Figures 5J-K) and the
521 loss of F-actin density upon CaMKII inhibition (Figures 5D-G), respectively. Collectively,
522 these data establish a functional link between Ca²⁺ signaling and F-actin regulation,
523 mediated by TRPV4 and CaMKII, that is imperative for the movement of cells.

524 The regulation of small GTPases by Ca^{2+} is fundamentally important, as it has been
525 shown to regulate the actin cytoskeleton in several cell types, such as fibroblasts⁸⁷,
526 osteosarcoma cells⁷⁴, *Xenopus* epithelium⁸⁸, and neurons^{85,89,90}. However, in most cell types,
527 the defined molecular pathways by which Ca^{2+} signals are transduced to small GTPases
528 have remained elusive. To address this, we first showed that TRPV4-regulated RhoA
529 activation is mediated by CaMKII (Figure 5). Then, by phosphoproteomic profiling of
530 purified lamellipodia fractions, we identified a RhoGEF, TEM4, that is responsible for
531 activating RhoA downstream of TRPV4 and CaMKII (Figure 6). The activation of RhoA by
532 TRPV4 in neurons has been recently reported^{91,92}, but the underlying molecular pathway of
533 such regulation is not known. Not only do we unravel the key molecular player, CaMKII, that
534 transduces signal from TRPV4 to RhoA (Figure 5), but importantly we also pinpoint a Ca^{2+} -
535 dependent RhoGEF, TEM4, that activates RhoA downstream of TRPV4 and CaMKII. These
536 data, for the first time, elucidate a complete molecular circuitry by which Ca^{2+} influx
537 regulates small GTPase activity and F-actin organization.

538 The role of Ca^{2+} in the regulation of lamellipodial protrusions has been previously
539 studied^{32,41}. The proposed model postulates that Ca^{2+} influx in protrusions activates Ca^{2+} -
540 dependent myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) that contracts the actin network and causes
541 retraction. While this model accounts for certain aspects of lamellipodia regulation, it does
542 not align with other findings that demonstrate a positive role of Ca^{2+} in protrusive
543 activity^{30,35,36,74,75}. Such discrepancies suggest that our current model of Ca^{2+} regulation in
544 lamellipodia is not accurate. The previous studies indicated that Ca^{2+} influx in protrusions,
545 which encompass both lamella and lamellipodia, triggers retraction^{32,41}. On the other hand,
546 our data show that a localized Ca^{2+} influx (within 2-3 μm of the cell edge), controlled by
547 TRPV4, facilitates F-actin assembly in lamellipodia and promotes protrusions. An
548 important, but often overlooked, distinction between our study and the previous studies is
549 in the precise location of the Ca^{2+} influx. This study, together with other studies^{32,41}, suggest
550 that contrary to previous beliefs that Ca^{2+} ion is a highly diffusive signaling cue⁷⁶, Ca^{2+}
551 signaling can be local and highly compartmentalized. Proximal Ca^{2+} signaling in
552 lamellipodia supports F-actin assembly and facilitates protrusion, while distal Ca^{2+}

553 signaling in lamella, which is enriched with myosin-II^{77,78}, causes the MLCK/myosin-II-
554 mediated retraction³². Such revised model of lamellipodia regulation by Ca²⁺ is also more
555 consistent with findings that myosin-II is unlikely to contract lamellipodial F-actin, due to
556 its suppression by tyrosine phosphorylation⁷⁹ and its low abundance in lamellipodia
557 (Figures S3A-B;⁷⁸. Based on the current literature and our results, we hypothesize that such
558 intricate compartmentalization of Ca²⁺ signaling is mediated by the local regulation of
559 stretch-activated channels, plasma membrane Ca²⁺ pumps, such as Ca²⁺-ATPase (PMCA)⁸⁰,
560 ER membrane Ca²⁺ channels⁸¹, and Ca²⁺ buffers^{82,83}. By spatially compartmentalizing a
561 signaling factor, such as the Ca²⁺ ion, the same signaling factor can take on different roles in
562 regulating lamellipodia protrusions. Understanding how Ca²⁺ signaling is spatially and
563 temporally compartmentalized will be an exciting avenue for future studies.

564 Despite the fact that TRPV4 is a mechano-gated ion channel, the mechanism of its
565 local mechano-activation remains unexplored in this study. To date, TRPV4 has been shown
566 to be activated by osmotic stimuli⁹³, mechanical strain⁹⁴, and thermal cues⁹⁵. While these
567 modes of TRPV4 activation are physiologically important, they are all relatively global cues,
568 making them unlikely to locally initiate the activation of TRPV4 in lamellipodia. We
569 hypothesize that TRPV4 is activated via a novel mechanism that allows for its local
570 activation in lamellipodia. Notably, several published studies have demonstrated that the
571 plasma membrane in lamellipodia is under high tension due to the pushing force generated
572 by actin polymerization⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸. While such local high membrane tension may mechanically
573 open mechano-gated channels like TRPV4, it still does not explain why TRPV4, specifically, is
574 activated instead of other stretch-activated channels. Based on our current understanding
575 of TRPV4's structure, we speculate that the specificity of TRPV4 activation in lamellipodia
576 may stem from the actin-binding motif present in C terminus of TRPV4^{99,100}. The actin-
577 binding motif may couple actin-dependent forces, such as actin retrograde flow in
578 lamellipodia¹⁰¹, to the activation of the channel, creating a positive feedback loop between
579 Ca²⁺ signaling and actin polymerization. Further work is required to determine the
580 necessity of TRPV4-actin interaction in the regulating its channel activity.

581 More broadly, our study has provided evidence that cells locally integrate different
582 signaling hubs to fine-tune the regulation of actin cytoskeleton. While this study primarily
583 focused on understanding how the crosstalk between Ca^{2+} and GTPase signaling regulates
584 F-actin organization in the context of cell migration, it is possible that a similar crosstalk
585 between Ca^{2+} and GTPase locally organizes F-actin in other cellular processes where Ca^{2+}
586 and GTPase signaling are important, such as membrane trafficking¹⁰² and cell-cell junction
587 formation¹⁰³. Furthermore, this study identifies potential therapeutic targets, including
588 TRPV4, CaMKII, and TEM4, which could be manipulated to alter the migration behaviour of
589 cells, such as immune and cancer cells.

590 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

591 **Figure 1. A mechano-gated Ca^{2+} -permeable ion channel, TRPV4, regulates** 592 **lamellipodial protrusions during cell spreading and migration**

593 (A) Ratiometric GCaMP6f/mCherry and Ftractin-emiRFP670 images of a spreading MEF.

594 (B) Quantification of lamellipodial GCaMP6f/mCherry intensity and cell edge displacement
595 speed. Each dot represents a spreading cell. $n = 10$ cells. The error bars indicate the
596 standard error (SE).

597 (C) Quantification of the relative Ca^{2+} levels in cell edge compared to cell body in 0.1%
598 DMSO- and 10 μM BAPTA-AM (in Ca^{2+} -free DMEM)-treated cells. $n \geq 6$ cells per condition.

599 (D-E) Effects of Ca^{2+} -perturbing drugs on cell spreading (D) DIC images of spreading cells
600 treated with 0.1% DMSO, 10 μM BAPTA-AM, 10 μM GdCl_3 , or 1 μM Thapsigargin. (E)
601 Quantification of cell spreading speeds. Each data point is normalized to the mean of its
602 control condition. $n \geq 15$ cells per condition.

603 (F) Quantification of cell spreading speeds upon siRNA depletion of individual TRP family
604 channels, TRPV4 inhibition (10 μM HC-067047), or Arp2/3 inhibition (100 μM CK-666). $n \geq$
605 15 cells per condition.

606 (G) DIC images and cell outlines of spreading MEFs treated with 0.1% DMSO or 10 μM HC-
607 067047.

608 (H-I) Analysis of the effects of TRPV4 suppression on lamellipodial protrusion speed (H)
609 DIC images and cell edge montages of migrating MEFs seed on fibronectin-coated glass
610 surface in control (siCtrl), TRPV4 depletion (siTRPV4), and rescue conditions. (I) Bar graph
611 of the average protrusion speed of migrating cells in control (siCtrl and DMSO), TRPV4
612 depletion (siTRPV4), rescue, and TRPV4 inhibition (TRPV4 inh.) conditions. $n \geq 20$ cells per
613 condition.

614 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
615 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
616 The data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) unless otherwise specified. * $p <$
617 0.05, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

618 See also Figures S1, S2, and Video S1.

619 **Figure 2. TRPV4 facilitates lamellipodial protrusions by locally controlling Ca^{2+} influx**

620 (A-C) Analysis of intracellular Ca^{2+} levels upon TRPV4 inhibition (A) Ratiometric
621 GCaMP6f/mCherry images of MEFs in 0.1% DMSO and TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μM HC-
622 067047) conditions. (B,C) Quantifications of the whole cell (B) and lamellipodial (C)
623 GCaMP6f/mCherry intensities in the presence of 0.1% DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μM
624 HC-067047) conditions. $n \geq 8$ cells per condition.

625 (D-F) Analysis of lamellipodial Ca^{2+} level upon acute TRPV4 inhibition (D) Ratiometric
626 GCaMP6f/mCherry and F-tractin-emiRFP670 images of a protruding cell edge before and
627 after TRPV4 inhibition. (E-F) Quantification of the percent change of lamellipodial
628 GCaMP6f/mCherry intensity in protruding (blue), quiescent (dark grey), and retracting
629 (red) phases of lamellipodia. The colored dot indicates the average value from multiple cells
630 and the individual values are in light grey. Each data point is normalized to the average
631 value of protrusion, stalling and retracting lamellipodia extracted from the same
632 kymograph. $n = 7$ cells per condition.

633 (G) Cross-correlation analysis between cell edge displacement and lamellipodial Ca^{2+} level.
634 The solid lines indicate the average cross-correlation values of multiple cells. $n \geq 9$ cells per
635 condition. The shaded area shows the standard error.

636 (H-I) Analysis of the effects of TRPV4 activation on the formation of lamellipodia (H) F-actin
637 and anti-cortactin images of cells treated with 0.1% DMSO, TRPV4 agonist (15 nM
638 GSK1016790A), or 1 μ M ionomycin for 5 mins. (I) Quantification of percent of cortactin-
639 positive cell edge in cells treated with 0.1% DMSO, TRPV4 agonist (15 nM GSK1016790A),
640 or 1 μ M ionomycin for 5 mins. n = 15 cells per condition.

641 (J-L) Analysis of the effect of photo-released Ca^{2+} on lamellipodia. (J) Quantification of
642 percent change in GCaMP6f intensity post-illumination of cells without (-) or with (+) NP-
643 EGTA-AM. n \geq 10 cells per condition.

644 (K) F-tractin-emiRFP670 and GCaMP6f images of cells pre- and post-illumination without (-
645) or with (+) NP-EGTA-AM. (L) Responses of cell edge post-illumination without (-) or with
646 (+) NP-EGTA-AM. 1 μ M ML-7 (a myosin light chain kinase inhibitor). The inhibition of
647 myosin light chain kinase was applied to avoid cell retraction caused by Ca^{2+} -dependent
648 myosin activation in the lamella³². n \geq 6 cells per condition.

649 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
650 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
651 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***
652 p < 0.005, **** p < 0.001.

653 See also Videos S2 and S3.

654 **Figure 3. TRPV4-mediated Ca^{2+} influx modulates F-actin density in lamellipodia**

655 (A-E) Analysis of lamellipodial F-actin and lamellipodia markers in MEFs. (A) Fluorescence
656 staining with phalloidin and anti-cortactin of MEFs treated with DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor.
657 (B) Quantifications of the F-actin intensity in lamellipodia in control conditions (DMSO and
658 siCtrl), and after TRPV4 inhibition or depletion. F-actin intensity of each cell is normalized
659 to the average intensity of control cells. n \geq 15 cells per condition. (C) Fluorescent
660 phalloidin and anti-ArpC2 images of cells treated with DMSO and TRPV4 inhibitor.
661 Quantifications of (D) lamellipodial cortactin intensity (n > 30 cells per condition) .and (E)
662 lamellipodial ArpC2 intensity upon TRPV4 inhibition (n \geq 7 cells per condition). Each cell's

663 cortactin/ArpC2 intensity is divided by the average of its control to get a normalized
664 intensity relative to its control.

665 (F-H) Analysis of lamellipodia F-actin architecture in MEFs using platinum replica electron
666 microscopy (PREM). (F) PREM (left and middle) and the segmented binary images (right)
667 of lamellipodia from MEFs treated with DMSO (top) or TRPV4 inhibitor (bottom).
668 Quantifications of lamellipodial F-actin meshwork porosity (G) and the average pore sizes
669 (H) in the presence of DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor. $n \geq 13$ cells per condition.

670 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
671 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
672 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
673 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

674 See also Figure S3.

675 **Figure 4. TRPV4 upregulates lamellipodial F-actin density via the RhoA/formins**
676 **pathway**

677 (A) Western blot showing the activity of RhoA in whole cell lysates treated with 0.1% DMSO
678 or TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047) by using the active GTPase pull-down assay.

679 (B-F) RhoA FRET analysis of control and TRPV4-inhibited cells. (B) Fluorescence images of
680 RhoA FRET biosensor activation and its distribution (acceptor channel). The white box
681 indicates the cell edge region used for kymograph analysis. (C) (Left) Zoomed RhoA FRET
682 images of the cell edge in the DMSO and TRPV4-inhibited cells. The white line indicates the
683 region used to create the kymograph on the right. (Right) Kymographs of protruding cell
684 edges in DMSO and TRPV4 inhibitor. (D) Line intensity profiles of RhoA FRET_{eff} across cell
685 edges in DMSO and TRPV4 inhibitor. (E) Quantifications of global RhoA FRET_{eff}. (F)
686 Quantifications of lamellipodia (LP)-to-cell body (CB) RhoA FRET_{eff}. $n \geq 10$ cells per
687 condition.

688 (G-H) Effects of RhoA/formins signaling pathway on lamellipodial F-actin. (G)
689 Quantifications of lamellipodial F-actin intensity in different conditions. $n > 15$ cells per
690 condition. (H) Fluorescent phalloidin staining images of cells treated with 0.1% DMSO,

691 TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047), Rho inhibitor (C3 transferase, 2.0 μ g/ml, 3 hrs), pan-
692 formins inhibitor (SMIFH2, 10 μ M, which has a negligible effect on myosin-II activity¹⁰⁴), or
693 a combination of TRPV4 and formins inhibitors.

694 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
695 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
696 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
697 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

698 See also Figure S4.

699 **Figure 5. TRPV4-regulated CaMKII signaling upregulates local RhoA activity and**
700 **facilitates cell protrusion.**

701 (A-C) Analysis of pCaMKII^{T286} level in MEFs treated with either 0.1% DMSO or TRPV4
702 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047). (A) Images of anti-pCaMKII^{T286} and fluorescent phalloidin
703 staining. (B) Quantifications of lamellipodial pCaMKII^{T286}. $n > 15$ cells per condition. (C) A
704 scatter plot of lamellipodial (LP) F-actin and pCaMKII intensities of individual cells treated
705 DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor. The black line indicates the best-fit linear regression.

706 (D-E) Effects of CaMKII inhibition (10 μ M KN-93) on F-actin intensity. (D) Fluorescent
707 phalloidin staining images of cells treated with DMSO, TRPV4 inhibitor, or CaMKII inhibitor.
708 (E) Quantifications of lamellipodial F-actin intensity. $n = 12$ cells per condition.

709 (F-G) Effects of phosphomimetic CaMKII (CaMKII α ^{T286D}) on F-actin in the presence of
710 TRPV4 inhibitor. (F) Fluorescent phalloidin and anti-cortactin staining images in cells
711 expressing wildtype CaMKII α in DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor, or CaMKII α ^{T286D} in TRPV4
712 inhibitor. (G) Quantifications of their LP F-actin intensity. $n > 15$ cells per condition.

713 (H-J) Effects of CaMKII inhibition on RhoA activity. (H) Quantifications of global RhoA
714 FRET_{eff} in cells treated with DMSO or CaMKII inhibitor ($n > 15$ cells per condition) and (I)
715 the average RhoA FRET intensity profiles extracted near the cell edges of cells treated with
716 DMSO or CaMKII inhibitor. $n = 15$ cells per condition. The shaded area shows the standard
717 error. The locations where the intensity profiles are taken are indicated in the

718 corresponding FRET images with white lines. (J) RhoA FRET images of MEFs treated with
719 DMSO or CaMKII inhibitor.

720 (K-L) Optogenetic inhibition of CaMKII in protruding cell edges using paAIP2. (K) (Left) DIC
721 images of cells without (-) or with (+) paAIP2 & DMSO. (Right) DIC images of cells with (+)
722 paAIP2 and TRPV4 inhibitor. The yellow box indicates the cell edge region used for the
723 zoomed-in shown on the right. The indicated time shows the time elapsed after the light
724 stimulation. The blue box indicates the light stimulation region. (L) Fractions of cells
725 undergoing protrusion, stalling, or retraction post stimulation. $n \geq 8$ cells per condition.
726 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
727 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
728 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
729 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

730 See also Figure S5 and Video S4.

731 **Figure 6. TEM4, a RhoGEF, regulates RhoA activity and lamellipodial protrusions as**
732 **part of the TRPV4/CaMKII signaling module.**

733 (A-C) Phosphoproteomic analysis of purified lamellipodia (LP) and cell body (CB) fractions.
734 (A) Schematic showing the general protocol of LP and CB fractionation. (B) DAPI and F-
735 actin fluorescence images of MEFs plated on the porous membrane in a transwell. (Left) 3D
736 projection from a 21 μm z-stack acquired at 0.25 μm steps. (Right) Maximum z projected
737 images of the top and bottom compartments.

738 (C) Scatterplot showing the abundance ratio of all the detected phosphopeptides from the
739 phosphoproteomic analysis. The y-axis represents the abundance ratio of TRPV4 inhibition
740 relative to the DMSO control, while the x-axis represents the abundance ratio of CaMKII
741 inhibition relative to the DMSO control. Each dot corresponds to a single phosphopeptide,
742 with blue dots indicating peptides that are commonly down-phosphorylated upon
743 inhibition of TRPV4 and CaMKII. $n = 3$ biological repeats.

744 (D) Quantifications of the cell spreading speed (relative to the mean of control) upon the
745 siRNA depletion of different RhoGEFs and RhoGAPs. $n \geq 45$ cells per condition.

746 (E) Quantifications of the protrusion speed of migrating MEFs in the control and upon
747 TEM4 depletion. $n > 25$ cells per condition.

748 (F-H) RhoA FRET analysis upon TEM4 depletion. (F) Fluorescence images of RhoA FRET
749 biosensor activation in control (siCtrl) and upon TEM4 depletion. (G) Quantifications of
750 global RhoA FRET_{eff}. $n > 20$ cells per condition. (H) Quantifications of lamellipodia (LP)-to-
751 cell body (CB) RhoA FRET_{eff}. $n \geq 14$ cells per condition.

752 (I) Quantifications of the F-actin intensity in lamellipodia of control (DMSO) and TEM4
753 depletion. Each cell's F-actin intensity is divided by the average of its control to get a
754 normalized actin intensity relative to its control. $n \geq 13$ cells per condition.

755 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
756 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
757 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
758 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

759 See also Figure S6.

760 **Figure 7. TRPV4/CaMKII/TEM4/RhoA signaling axis regulates cell migration**

761 (A-E) Analysis of the role of TRPV4 signaling axis on random cell migration on fibronectin
762 (FN)-coated substrate in 20 hours. (A) Schematic of the experimental setup for the random
763 migration assay. (B) Migration tracks of MEFs treated with 0.1% DMSO, TRPV4 inhibitor
764 (10 μ M HC-067047), non-targeting siRNA (control), or TEM4 siRNA. The black dot indicates
765 the end of the track. Only cell tracks that were continuously tracked for 40 frames were
766 displayed. (C) DIC and fluorescence images of MEFs transiently expressing mEmerald-
767 tagged Histone H2B with the migration tracks overlay. The white and red dotted lines
768 indicate the track length (D) and the Euclidean distance (d), respectively. (D)
769 Quantifications of the average migration speed upon TRPV4 inhibition, and TEM4 depletion
770 and (E) their directionality. $n \geq 24$ cells per condition.

771 (F-H) Analysis of the role of TRPV4 signaling axis on 3D migration in 12 hours. (F)
772 Schematic of the experimental setup for the 3D collagen migration assay, in which MEFs
773 stably expressing PH-Akt-eGFP were embedded in the collagen I matrix prior to imaging.

774 (G) Maximum z-projected fluorescent phalloidin staining and second harmonic generation
775 (SHG) images of MEFs embedded in a collagen matrix. (H) Quantifications of average cell
776 migration speed of MEFs stained for Hoechst embedded in collagen matrices. MEFs were
777 treated with TRPV4 inhibition or TEM4 depletion. n = 40 cells per condition.

778 (I-J) Effects of TRPV4 inhibition on melanoblast migration *ex vivo*. (I) Schematic of the
779 experimental setup for the mouse melanoblast migration assay. (J) Fluorescence images of
780 melanoblasts from *Mitf-Cre::Rosa26-floxed stop-TdTomato* E15.5 embryo trunk skin explant
781 with or without TRPV4 inhibitor. (K) Quantifications of the average melanoblast migration
782 speed in control and upon TRPV4 inhibition. (L) Melanoblast migration tracks in the mouse
783 skin explants. (M-N) Quantifications of net displacement and mean protrusion velocity
784 upon TRPV4 inhibition. n ≥ 74 cells per condition.

785 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
786 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
787 The data are presented as mean ± SD unless otherwise specified. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***
788 p < 0.005, **** p < 0.001.

789 See also Figure S7, Videos S5 and S6.

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1151 **METHODS**

1152 **Cell Culture**

1153 Mouse embryo fibroblasts (MEFs) were obtained from Dr. Beckerle (University of
1154 Utah). U-2 OS human osteosarcoma cells (U2OS) were obtained from Dr. Waterman (NIH).
1155 MDA-MB-231 and HeLa cells were obtained from Dr. Chen (Johns Hopkins University).
1156 MEFs and MDA-MB-231 cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 2 mM L-
1157 glutamine, 100 U/mL penicillin/streptomycin and 10% FBS (Wisent Bioproducts). HeLa
1158 cells were cultured in EMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 100 U/mL
1159 penicillin/streptomycin. All cells were maintained at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO₂
1160 incubator.

1161 **Transfections, Plasmids, siRNA treatment**

1162 For the experiments that require transient plasmid expression or siRNA-mediated
1163 depletion (200 nM of each siRNA), cells were transfected using Nucleofector 2b (Lonza
1164 Bioscience) with a custom transfection solution (5 mM KCl, 15 mM MgCl₂, 120 mM
1165 Na₂HPO₄/NaH₂PO₄ (pH 7.2), 50 mM mannitol) and program T-020. Transfected cells were
1166 plated on glass-bottom imaging dishes (Cellvis, Cat.: D35-20-1.5-N) or coverslips that were
1167 coated with 2.5 mg/mL human fibronectin (EMD Millipore, Cat.: FC010) in PBS for 1 hour at
1168 37 °C.

1169 **Immunofluorescence**

1170 Cells seeded on acid-washed coverslips (Corning) were fixed in 4% EM-grade
1171 paraformaldehyde (Electron Microscopy Sciences, Cat.: 15700) diluted in cytoskeleton
1172 buffer (10 mM MES (pH 6.1), 138 mM KCl, 3 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM EGTA, 0.32 M sucrose) for 30
1173 min at room temperature and washed with PBS. After fixation, cells were permeabilized
1174 with 0.1% (v/v) Triton X-100 in PBS for 10 mins, washed and blocked in 2% (w/v) BSA
1175 (BioShop) in PBS. Coverslips were incubated overnight at 4 °C with primary antibodies
1176 (1:100) diluted in the blocking solution. The primary antibodies used for
1177 immunofluorescence in this study were: anti-ArpC2 (Millipore Sigma, 07-227), anti-
1178 Cortactin (Cell Signaling, 3503S), anti-pS19MLC2 (Cell Signaling, 3674S), anti-eGFP (Cell

1179 Signaling, 2555S), anti-pCaMKII (Abcam, ab32678). On the next day, they were washed with
1180 PBST, and incubated for 1 hour with fluorophore-conjugated secondary antibodies (1:200,
1181 Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories) and Alexa Fluor488-conjugated phalloidin
1182 (ThermoFisher, Cat.: A12379) in the blocking solution. The stained samples were washed
1183 with PBST, mounted on microscope slides in an aqueous mounting media (Fluoromount,
1184 Sigma-Aldrich, Cat.: F4680) and sealed with a nail polish.

1185 **Measurements of lamellipodial F-actin, ArpC2, cortactin, pCaMKII intensities, and** 1186 **lamellipodia perimeter**

1187 MEFs co-stained with phalloidin and anti-cortactin, anti-pCaMKII, or anti-ArpC2,
1188 were imaged using a spinning disk confocal microscope. To account for local changes in
1189 image intensity due to membrane ruffles near cell edges, a 1.2 μm confocal z-stack was
1190 captured. To prepare images for intensity analysis, the z-stack images of F-actin,
1191 lamellipodia marker (e.g., ArpC2 and cortactin), or pCaMKII were maximum projected and
1192 background subtracted using a custom Python script
1193 (`background_subtraction_nd2_images.py`). To measure the intensities of F-actin and
1194 lamellipodia markers, ROIs were created in Fiji/ImageJ, by manually outlining the
1195 lamellipodia on the processed images. The mean grayscale value within the ROI was
1196 reported as the F-actin, ArpC2, or cortactin intensity accordingly.

1197 **Recombinant DNA Generation and Site-directed Mutagenesis**

1198 All the plasmids generated in this paper were created using restriction enzymes
1199 cloning. Primers were purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT), and the
1200 sequence of interest was confirmed by Sanger sequencing (TCAG DNA Sequencing Facility)
1201 and whole-plasmid sequencing (Plasmidsaurus). Sequences of interest were amplified by
1202 PCR from other vectors (Addgene) using Phusion polymerase (NEB, Cat.: M0530) and
1203 oligonucleotide primers. All primers are listed in Supplementary Table 1. The PCR
1204 amplicons were restriction-digested (restriction enzymes from New England Biolabs, NEB),
1205 purified using gel band or column purification kits (Qiagen), and ligated with T4 ligase
1206 (NEB, Cat.: M0202).

1207 All the site-directed mutagenesis was performed based on a modified protocol¹⁰⁵.
1208 The single-primer PCRs were performed using Q5 polymerase (NEB, Cat.: M0491) in the
1209 KOD polymerase buffer (Millipore Sigma, Cat.: 71975).

1210 **Reverse Transcription PCR (RT-PCR)**

1211 The total RNA of MEFs was isolated and reverse transcribed into cDNA (SuperScript
1212 II), then PCR (DreamTaq) was performed to detect TRP channel expression. All primers are
1213 listed in Supplementary Table 1.

1214 **Microscopy and Live Cell Imaging**

1215 All timelapse imaging of live cells was performed with cells incubated at 37°C with a
1216 humidified stage-top incubator and an objective heater (Tokai Hit). For most live cell
1217 imaging experiments, phenol red-free DMEM media (Wisent) supplemented with 25 mM
1218 HEPES (Wisent), 10% FBS (Wisent), 100 U/mL penicillin/streptomycin (Wisent), 10 mM
1219 DL-lactate (Millipore Sigma, Cat.: 71720), and OxyFluor (Oxyrase, Cat.: OF-0005).

1220 Images of live and immunolabeled cells were acquired on an Eclipse Ti2-E inverted
1221 microscope (Nikon Instruments) equipped with a 10×/0.3 NA Plan Fluor DLL (for phase
1222 contrast imaging of cell spreading), 20×/0.75 NA Super Fluor (for higher magnification DIC
1223 imaging of cell spreading and migration), or 100×/1.4 NA CFI Plan Apochromat Lambda D
1224 (for IF imaging and calcium imaging) objective, a dynamic focusing system to correct for
1225 focus drift (PFS, Nikon Instruments), a CREST X-Light V2 LFOV25 (CrestOptics), a 7-color
1226 Celesta light engine (Lumencor) and a Prime95b sCmos camera (Photometrics).

1227 For the light stimulation imaging experiments, images of cells were acquired on an
1228 Eclipse Ti2-E inverted microscope (Nikon Instruments) equipped with a 60× objective, a
1229 dynamic focusing system to correct for focus drift (PFS; Nikon Instruments), a dual
1230 galvanometer laser scanner (Bruker Corporation), and a LunF laser combiner with 100mW
1231 405nm and 488nm solid state lasers (Nikon Instruments).

1232 Images of cell cultured in three-dimensional collagen gel were acquired by an
1233 Eclipse FN1 upright microscope (Nikon Instruments) equipped with an A1R-MP confocal
1234 scanner, a femtosecond infrared laser (Chameleon Vision II, Coherent) and 25× CFI Apo NA

1235 1.1 LWD objective. Second harmonic generation signal emitted by collagen fibers was
1236 collected with a non-descanned GaAsP epi-detector after it was isolated from the laser
1237 fundamental and any fluorescence by a 474nm bandpass filter (28 nm full width half-
1238 maximum; Semrock Inc, Cat.: FF-01-474/23nm BrightLine).

1239 **Western Blotting**

1240 Cell lysates were obtained by rinsing the cells with ice-cold PBS and then scraping
1241 them into RIPA buffer (150 mM NaCl, 1% (v/v) Nonidet P-40, 0.5% (w/v) DOC, 0.1% (w/v)
1242 SDS, 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.4)) supplemented with protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche, Cat.:
1243 11697498001) and phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Roche, Cat.: 4906845001). The lysates
1244 were sheared by running through a 25G needle 10 times and then cleared by centrifugation
1245 (17,900 $\times g$, 25 min, 4°C). Proteins from supernatants were quantified by the BCA method.
1246 30 μg of proteins were mixed with an equal volume of 2 \times Laemmli sample buffer and
1247 separated by a homemade SDS-PAGE gels (8% - 12% polyacrylamide was used as the
1248 resolving gel depending on the size of proteins of interest. 4% polyacrylamide was used as
1249 the stacking gel) in Tris-glycine running buffer (Wisent, Cat.: 811-560-FL) at 30 mA and
1250 then electro-transferred to PVDF membranes (Millipore Sigma, Cat.: ISEQ10100) overnight
1251 at 15 V for proteins smaller than 40 kDa or 90 V for 60 mins for proteins bigger than 40
1252 kDa. Following transfer, the membranes were blocked for 1 hour. For fluorescence
1253 detection, TBS Blocking Buffer (Licor, Cat.: 927-60001) was used. For chemiluminescence
1254 detection, 5% (w/v) BSA (Wisent) in TBST (Wisent, Cat.: 811-030-FL, 1 \times buffer
1255 supplemented with 0.1% (v/v) Tween-20) was used. After blocking, the membranes were
1256 incubated with respective primary and secondary antibodies conjugated to far-red
1257 fluorophores (LI-COR) for fluorescent antibody detection or secondary antibodies labeled
1258 with HRP in blocking buffer (TBST + 5% BSA) for chemiluminescence detection.
1259 Fluorescently labelled membranes were washed with TBST and imaged with the Odyssey®
1260 Fc imaging system (LI-COR). HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies were visualized using
1261 enhanced chemiluminescent (ECL) horseradish peroxidase (HRP) substrate (ThermoFisher,
1262 Cat.: 34580). The antibodies and dilutions used for western blotting in this study were:
1263 anti-TRPV4 (1:1000, Abcam, ab39260), anti-Vimentin (1:1000, Cell Signaling, 5741S), anti-

1264 RhoA (1:500, Cytoskeleton, ARH05), anti-Rac1 (1:500, Cytoskeleton, ARC03), anti-Cdc42
1265 (1:250, Cytoskeleton, ACD03B), anti-pCaMKII (1:1000, Abcam, ab32678), anti-Vinculin
1266 (1:1000, MilliporeSigma, V9131), anti-VASP (1:1000, Cell Signaling, 3132T). Secondary
1267 antibodies: For chemiluminescence detection, HRP-conjugated Donkey anti-mouse IgG or
1268 anti-rabbit IgG were used at a dilution 1:10,000, in 2% BSA blocking buffer (Jackson
1269 Immuno Research). For fluorescent antibody detection, IRDye (680 nm or 800 nm)-
1270 conjugated anti-mouse IgG or anti-rabbit IgG were used at a dilution 1:10,000 in TBS
1271 blocking buffer (LI-COR). Visualization and quantification of western blots was performed
1272 using ImageStudio (LI-COR).

1273 **Platinum replica electron microscopy (PREM) and EM image analysis**

1274 Sample processing for PREM was performed as described previously^{106,107}. In brief,
1275 cells were seeded on glass coverslips coated with 2.5 µg/mL fibronectin. After 1 hour of
1276 drug treatment in culture, cells were extracted for 4 minutes with 1% Triton X-100 in PEM
1277 buffer (100 mM PIPES, pH 6.9; 1 mM EGTA; 1 mM MgCl₂) supplemented with 2 µM
1278 phalloidin and 2 µM taxol and fixed with 2% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M Na-cacodylate buffer
1279 (pH 7.3) for 20 minutes. The samples were post-fixed by sequential treatment with
1280 aqueous 0.1% tannic acid and 0.2% uranyl acetate, then critical-point dried, coated with
1281 platinum and carbon, transferred onto EM grids and examined using JEM 1011
1282 transmission electron microscope (JEOL USA, Peabody, MA) operated at 100 kV. Images
1283 were acquired by an ORIUS 832.10 W CCD camera driven by Gatan Digital Micrograph 1.8.4
1284 software (Gatan, Warrendale, PA) and presented in inverted contrast.

1285 The EM images were processed and analyzed using a custom-built Python script
1286 (skeleton_EM.py) and Fiji/ImageJ. Firstly, a Gaussian blur was applied to the EM images to
1287 reduce noise. This was followed by a top hat transformation to enhance the filamentous
1288 features of the images. To segment the F-actin-positive pixels from the enhanced images, K-
1289 means clustering was used. Porosity was calculated as the percent of F-actin-negative pixels
1290 in the field of view. The average pore size was calculated by measuring the average size of
1291 holes devoid of F-actin using the analyze particles function in Fiji/ImageJ.

1292 **Cell Spreading Assay and Cell Spreading Speed Measurement**

1293 The cell spreading assay was performed as previously described¹⁰⁸. DIC images of
1294 spreading cells were analyzed in Fiji/ImageJ. To measure the cell spreading speed of MEFs,
1295 we created kymographs (averaging 3 pixels in width) that capture cell edge movements.
1296 The average cell spreading speed was quantified by measuring the slope of the initial fast
1297 spreading phase. To compare datapoints from experimental treatments and different
1298 biological replica, we normalized the each datapoint to the mean cell spreading speed of
1299 their corresponding control condition, resulting in percent change in cell spreading speed
1300 relative to control.

1301 **Lamellipodia Protrusion Speed of Migrating Cells**

1302 MEFs were plated on 2.5 µg/mL fibronectin-coated coverslips overnight prior to the
1303 experiment. To visualize the cell edge with high temporal and spatial resolution in a less
1304 invasive manner, we employed DIC timelapse imaging with an imaging interval of 3 seconds
1305 for 20 minutes. Protrusion speed was analyzed by creating a kymograph (averaging 3 pixels
1306 in width) for each cell using the KymoResliceWide plugin in Fiji/ImageJ. The average
1307 protrusion speed of each cell was quantified by measuring the slope of each protrusion
1308 event.

1309 **Calcium Imaging**

1310 To visual F-actin and intracellular Ca²⁺ level simultaneously, MEFs were transfected
1311 with mCherry-T2A-GCaMP6f and Ftractin-emiRFP670, and cultured overnight in 2.5 µg/mL
1312 fibronectin-coated glass-bottom dishes. Cells were then transferred to an imaging media
1313 supplemented with DMSO or HC-067047 for 1 hour prior to imaging (unless otherwise
1314 specified). Confocal timelapse images were acquired using a 100×/1.4 NA objective.

1315 To record changes in the F-actin and intracellular Ca²⁺ level before and after a drug
1316 treatment, e.g., TRPV4 inhibitor or ionomycin, the transfected cells were imaged every 10
1317 seconds for 5 minutes in the presence of DMSO. Then, an equal volume of imaging media
1318 supplemented with 2× drug was added quickly to sides of the glass bottom dish with a
1319 micropipettor. Image acquisition resumed for an additional 10 to 15 minutes.

1320 **RhoGTPase FRET Biosensors Imaging**

1321 To assess the subcellular activity of GTPases (RhoA, Rac1 and Cdc42), MEFs were
1322 transfected with pTriExRhoA2G (Addgene #40176), pTriEx4-Rac1-2G (Addgene #66110),
1323 or pTriEx4-Cdc42-2G (Addgene #68814) respectively. The transfected cells were cultured
1324 in 2.5 µg/mL fibronectin-coated glass bottom dishes overnight. To inhibit TRPV4 or CaMKII,
1325 the transfected cells were switched to an imaging medium composed of live cell imaging
1326 solution (Invitrogen, Cat.: A59688DJ), 2% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin/streptomycin, 10 mM
1327 HEPES, 10 mM DL-lactate, OxyFluor, and the inhibitor of choice 1 hour before imaging.
1328 Widefield timelapse images were acquired using a 60×/1.2 NA Plan Apo VC water
1329 immersion objective every 3 minutes for 20 minutes.

1330 **Ratiometric Image Analysis for GCaMP6f/mCherry Intensity and Rho GTPase FRET_{eff}**

1331 All the ratiometric image analyses were performed using custom-built Python
1332 scripts (get_ratiometric_map for Ca²⁺ image analysis or FRET_get_ratiometric_map for
1333 FRET image analysis). These scripts were written based on published ratiometric image
1334 analysis pipelines^{109,110}. All images were shading corrected using a cell-free reference
1335 image. Images from each channel were aligned using the optical flow registration
1336 algorithm. The aligned images were then background-subtracted by each image's
1337 background value. The background value was measured by taking the median of the
1338 background pixels estimated using the Otsu method. For FRET image analysis,
1339 bleedthrough correction is applied at this stage. A gaussian filter ($\sigma = 0.5$) was applied to
1340 each image to reduce noise. Then, the numerator channel (the GCaMP or the FRET channel)
1341 was divided by the denominator channel (the mCherry or the CFP channel) to obtain the
1342 ratiometric image. We routinely multiple the ratiometric image by 1000 to stay within the
1343 16-bit depth. Images of the F-tractin or YFP channel were segmented and binarized using K-
1344 means segmentation ($k = 3$ or 4 depending on the image intensity). The binary mask was
1345 applied to the corresponding ratiometric image to remove the background spurious pixels
1346 after the image division. As an optional step, a photobleaching correction can be applied to
1347 the ratiometric images by the double exponential method.

1348 For the FRET image analysis, the following equation was used to remove light bleed-
1349 through into channels where it is not desirable.

1350
$$\text{Corrected FRET}_{eff} = \frac{\text{FRET}_{raw} - (\alpha \times m\text{TFP1}) - (\beta \times m\text{Venus})}{m\text{TFP1}}$$

1351 where Corrected FRET_{eff} is the corrected FRET efficiency, FRET_{raw} is the total FRET
1352 intensity as measured, α is the bleed-through coefficient of mTFP1 into the FRET channel
1353 upon mTFP1 (440 nm) excitation, β is the bleed-through coefficient of mVenus into FRET
1354 channel upon mVenus (514 nm) excitation, and mTFP1 is the total mTFP1 intensity as
1355 measured. MEFs transiently expressing either mTFP1 alone or mVenus alone are used to
1356 determine α and β . To obtain α and β , we measured the fluorescence values of mTFP1 or
1357 mVenus and FRET channels from many cells expressing either mTFP1 alone or mVenus
1358 alone. The slope of mTFP1 or mVenus intensity and FRET channel intensity curve is α and
1359 β , respectively. For our microscope and exposure conditions, the α parameter was found to
1360 be 0.3072 and the β parameter to be 0.05228.

1361 **Correlation analysis of cell edge displacement and Ca²⁺ level**

1362 The cross-correlation analysis was based on a published study¹¹¹. To obtain the
1363 spatial and temporal information of cell edge displacement and Ca²⁺ activity, we created
1364 kymographs using (averaging 3 pixels in width) for each cell using the KymoResliceWide
1365 plugin in Fiji/ImageJ based on the ratiometric Ca²⁺ images. Then, the kymograph was
1366 imported into and analyzed by a custom Python script
1367 (quantify_cell_edge_velocity_and_calcium.py). To compute the cross-correlation of cell edge
1368 displacement and Ca²⁺ level, we needed a cell edge displacement-time graph and a Ca²⁺-
1369 time graph. The cell edge displacement-time graph was extracted from the kymograph by
1370 tracking the cell edge position over time. The Ca²⁺-time graph was extracted by measuring
1371 the average intensity of the 4 pixels (~1.5 μm) closest the cell edge. These two graphs were
1372 Gaussian-filtered ($\sigma = 1$) before the cross-correlation analysis. The cross-correlation
1373 coefficient was computed by the np.correlate function and the delay times by the
1374 scipy.signal.correlation_lags function. An optional spline fitting was applied to smoothen
1375 the curve in the cross-correlation graph.

1376 **RhoA/Rac1/Cdc42 Pull-Down Activation Assay**

1377 All the GTPase pull-down activation experiments were performed using a
1378 commercial GTPase kit (Cytoskeleton, Cat.: BK030) and according to the manufacturer's
1379 instructions.

1380 **Photo-Release of Ca²⁺ using NP-EGTA-AM**

1381 To visual changes in Ca²⁺ upon local Ca²⁺ release, MEFs were transfected with
1382 mCherry-T2A-GCaMP6f, and cultured overnight in 2.5 µg/mL fibronectin-coated glass-
1383 bottom dishes. 10 µM NP-EGTA-AM (Invitrogen, Cat.: N6802) dissolved in DMSO
1384 supplemented with 0.1% Pluronic was added to the cells 2 hours before imaging. For DIC
1385 and fluorescence imaging, cells were switched to the imaging media supplemented with 1
1386 µM ML-7 (a myosin light chain kinase inhibitor). The inhibition of myosin light chain kinase
1387 was applied to avoid cell retraction caused by Ca²⁺-dependent myosin activation in the
1388 lamella³².

1389 The whole sample preparation was performed with limited light exposure to avoid
1390 the activation of NP-EGTA-AM. To visualize the intracellular Ca²⁺ level and cell edge activity
1391 without photoactivation of NP-EGTA-AM or photodamaging to the cells, only DIC and the
1392 GCaMP6f channels were recorded. Timelapse images were captured every 3 seconds for 30
1393 seconds before the light stimulation and for 2 minutes after the light stimulation. To photo-
1394 release Ca²⁺, we illuminated the cell in a small region (3×3 µm) of the cytoplasm directly
1395 adjacent to the stalling cell edge with a low-intensity 405 nm laser for 3 seconds.

1396 **CaMKII Photoinactivation**

1397 To inhibit CaMKII locally with light stimulation, we adopted an optogenetic inhibitor
1398 of CaMKII (paAIP2)^{58,62}. To create an expression construct of paAIP2 for MEFs, we excised
1399 out the P2A-paAIP2 fragment from the construct, CaMKIIP-mEGFP-P2A-paAIP2/pAAV
1400 (Addgene #91718), and inserted it to another DNA expression construct, Histone H2B-
1401 eBFP2 (Addgene #55243), resulting in the expression construct, H2B-eBFP2-P2A-paAIP2.
1402 MEFs were transfected with H2B-eBFP2-P2A-paAIP2 and plated in fibronectin-coated
1403 glass-bottom dishes overnight. The H2B-eBFP2 was used to as an indicator of the
1404 expression of paAIP2.

1405 Timelapse DIC images were captured every 3 seconds for 30 seconds before the light
1406 stimulation and for 2 minutes after the light stimulation. To assess the response of a
1407 protruding lamellipodia to the inhibition of CaMKII, we illuminated the cell in a small
1408 region (3×3 μm) of the cytoplasm directly adjacent to the protruding cell edge with a low-
1409 intensity 405 nm laser for 3 seconds.

1410 **Purification of lamellipodia and cell body fractionation**

1411 The lamellipodia and cell body fractionation was performed based on a modified
1412 published protocol⁶⁶. Briefly, MEFs were plated on a 3-μm porous polycarbonate membrane
1413 (Millipore Sigma, Cat.: CLS3464) pre-coated with fibronectin. After cell attachment, the
1414 cells were starved in 1% FBS media overnight. a serum gradient (1% in the inner
1415 compartment and 10% in the outer compartment) was applied overnight prior to methanol
1416 fixation. The lamellipodia (LP) fraction was first harvested manually with a cotton swab.
1417 The cotton swab was subsequently placed in RIPA buffer to solubilize the proteins. Then,
1418 the cell body (CB) fraction was extracted by placing the remaining membrane in RIPA
1419 buffer. Protein concentration in all samples was measured by the BCA method. To validate
1420 the fractionation of lamellipodia and cell body, we routinely compare the abundance of
1421 VASP, as a lamellipodia marker, in LP and CB fractions using Western blot.

1422 **Random Migration Assay and Cell Tracking**

1423 To fluorescently label MEFs for automated cell tracking, cells were transfected with
1424 Histone H2B-mEmerald. After transfection, cells were seeded onto 2.5 μg/mL fibronectin-
1425 coated coverslips overnight prior to the experiment. Cells seeded on coverslips were placed
1426 in a Chamlide CMS magnetic chamber (Quorum Technologies). DIC and fluorescence images
1427 were acquired through a 20× DIC objective every 12 minutes for 20 hours.

1428 The timelapse images of the fluorescently labelled nuclei (Histone-H2B-mEmerald)
1429 were analyzed using the Fiji plugin TrackMate¹¹². The nuclei were first identified using the
1430 LoG detector (estimated object diameter: 25 μm, quality threshold: 0.08). After that, the
1431 LAP tracker algorithm (max distance: 50 μm, Gap closing max distance and max frame gap:
1432 50 μm and 3 frames) was used to link the same nuclei in different timeframes. This

1433 generated tracks that were subsequently filtered by the track length and total distance
1434 traveled, restricting the analysis to cells that lasted at least 5 frames and traveled as least 18
1435 μm . All the tracks were manually terminated as soon as the cell started to divide. Lastly, the
1436 spots table, which contains the temporal and positional information of each track, was
1437 exported as .csv files. To compute different cell migration parameters, e.g., average
1438 migration speed and directionality, and visualize the tracks on a graph, the .csv files were
1439 analyzed using a custom-built Python script (trackmate_csv.py).

1440 **Collagen Matrix Preparation, Morphological Analysis, and Migration in 3D** 1441 **Microenvironment**

1442 Collagen matrices were prepared according to published protocols^{113,114}. Briefly, 35-
1443 mm glass bottom dishes were first silanized by (3-aminopropyl) trimethoxysilane (APTMS,
1444 Millipore Sigma, Cat.: 281778) and activated by glutaraldehyde (Electron Microscopy
1445 Sciences, Cat.: 16220). Then, in the activated glass bottom dishes, 3 mg/mL of collagen gel I
1446 solution (Corning, Cat.: 354249) was mixed with suspended MEFs. The cell/collagen
1447 mixture was allowed to polymerize at 21°C. Once a collagen sponge was formed, it was
1448 transferred to a humidified, 37°C, 5% CO₂ incubator overnight prior to imaging.

1449 For the morphological analysis of cells embedded in collagen gels, MEFs stably
1450 expressing PH-Akt-eGFP were either pre-treated with 0.1% DMSO, 10 μM TRPV4 inhibitor
1451 for 1 hour before imaging, or transfected with siRNA (siCtrl or siTEM4) overnight before
1452 imaging. High magnification z-stacks of individual cells were used to measure the number
1453 of branches and cell aspect ratio in Fiji/ImageJ.

1454 For the migration assay in 3D collagen gel, the nuclei of MEFs were labelled with 50
1455 ng/mL Hoechst and cell migration was monitored over 12 hours using time-lapse
1456 microscopy with images captured every 30 minutes. The displacement of the cell centroid
1457 from the initial position was quantified using Fiji/ImageJ. The 3D migration speed was
1458 calculated by dividing the cell displacement by the duration of the cell track.

1459 **Visualization of Melanoblast Migration in Mouse Embryonic Skin live *ex vivo***

1460 To label embryonic melanoblasts, a melanocyte-specific *Mitf-Cre* transgene was used
1461 to induce *TdTomato* expression from a *Rosa26-floxed stop-TdTomato* fluorescent reporter.
1462 E15.5 embryos were harvested, and the intact epidermis and dermis were isolated from the
1463 embryonic trunk skin. The skin explant was then sandwiched so that the epidermis was in
1464 contact with a gas permeable Lumox membrane in a 35 mm dish and the dermis was in
1465 contact with a 1% agarose pad made with complete phenol-free DMEM. Finally, the
1466 sandwich setup was overlaid with 1 mL complete phenol-free DMEM and weighted for
1467 imaging. For the TRPV4 inhibitor treatment group, the skin explants were incubated with
1468 complete phenol-free DMEM with 10 μ M TRPV4 inhibitor for 2 hrs before imaging. Skin
1469 explants were imaged live using a 20X objective with a stage top incubator at 37°C on an
1470 Olympus Fluoview (FV1000) inverted confocal microscope.

1471 Melanoblasts movies were analyzed using the ImageJ ADAPT plugin, and single cells
1472 were tracked throughout the duration of the entire movie.

1473 **Focal Adhesion Imaging and Image Analyses**

1474 To visualize focal adhesion protein, paxillin, in MEFs, we transfected the cells with
1475 Paxillin-eGFP (Addgene #15233), fixed, and co-stained cells with anti-GFP (Abcam, Cat.:
1476 ab13970) and fluorescent phalloidin (Invitrogen, Cat.: A12380). A TIRF microscope paired
1477 with an oil immersion 100 \times /1.49 NA Apo TIRF objective was used to image paxillin.

1478 To suppress the background signal in the paxillin images, a rolling ball background
1479 subtraction (radius = 20 pixels/2.2 μ m) was applied. To segment the paxillin-positive
1480 pixels, K-means clustering (K = 3) was used. The segmented adhesion mask was hole-filled,
1481 eroded with a disk kernel (1 pixel/0.11 μ m), and size-filtered to refine the mask and
1482 remove objects smaller than 15 pixels/0.2 μ m². The individual focal adhesion size and
1483 number were measured using the `skimage.measure.regionprops` function.

1484 To segment the outline of the cell, K-means clustering (K = 4) was applied on the F-
1485 actin image. The segmented cell mask was hole-filled, eroded with a disk kernel (1
1486 pixel/0.11 μ m), and size-filtered to refine the mask and remove objects smaller than 5000

1487 pixels/60 μm^2 . The total area occupied by paxillin-positive pixels divided by the area of the
1488 cell is reported as the total adhesive area.

1489 All the processing and quantifications procedures were performed using a custom
1490 Python script (adhesions_segmentation.py).

1491 **Quantification and Statistical Analysis**

1492 Statistical analyses were performed with GraphPad Prism software. Details of
1493 statistical operations performed in figures are presented in their corresponding figure
1494 legend.

1495 **SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE AND VIDEO CAPTIONS**

1496 **Figure S1. Perturbations in Ca^{2+} signaling, by Ca^{2+} drugs or TRPV4 inhibitor, affects**
1497 **cell spreading independently of integrin signaling. Related to Figure 1.**

1498 (A) 3D projection of a MEF in 3 different stages (early, middle and late) of cell spreading.
1499 (Left) Fluorescent phalloidin and (Right) anti-ArpC2 staining. The images are color-coded
1500 based on the z-depth.

1501 (B-F) Effects of Ca^{2+} ionophore, chelator and sarco-endoplasmic reticulum ATPases
1502 inhibitor on cell spreading. Timelapse ratiometric GCaMP6f/mCherry and Ftractin-
1503 emiRFP670 images of a spreading cell treated with (B) 10 μM BAPTA-AM and (C) 1 μM
1504 ionomycin. Quantifications of (D) the lamellipodial GCaMP6f/mCherry intensity and (E) the
1505 average cell spreading speed before and after the addition of ionomycin. $n \geq 9$ cells per
1506 condition. (F) Timelapse ratiometric GCaMP6f/mCherry and Ftractin-emiRFP670 images of
1507 a spreading cell treated with 1 μM thapsigargin.

1508 (G) Reverse transcription PCR (RT-PCR) analysis of TRP family channels expressed in MEFs.
1509 The TRP channels that are labelled in dark and light green are Ca^{2+} -conducting and non
1510 Ca^{2+} -conducting, respectively.

1511 (H-I) Effects of poly-D-lysine coated substrate on cell spreading. (H) DIC timelapse images
1512 of spreading MEFs treated with (top) DMSO and (bottom) TRPV4 inhibitor. The colored

1513 outline shows the cell boundary. (I) Quantifications of cell spread area over time in DMSO
1514 and TRPV4 inhibitor conditions. n = 20 cells per condition.

1515 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
1516 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
1517 The data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p <
1518 0.005, **** p < 0.001.

1519 **Figure S2. Suppression of TRPV4 impedes cell spreading across different cell types**
1520 **and downregulates lamellipodia formation. Related to Figure 1.**

1521 (A-C) Quantifications of (A) U2OS, (B) HeLa and (C) MDA-MB-231 cell spread area over
1522 time in the presence of DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor. n = 20 cells per condition.

1523 (D-F) Western blot analysis of endogenous TRPV4 level in siCtrl, siTRPV4, and rescue
1524 treatments 24 hours post-transfection. (D) Western blots showing the TRPV4 knockdown
1525 efficiencies of individual siRNAs and (E) a combination of TRPV4 siRNAs #2 and #4. (F)
1526 Quantifications of TRPV4 knockdown efficiency. n = 3 biological repeats.

1527 (G-H) Analysis of percent of ArpC2-enriched cell edge upon TRPV4 suppression. (G)
1528 Fluorescent phalloidin and anti-ArpC2 images of cells treated with 0.1% DMSO and TRPV4
1529 inhibitor. (H) Quantifications of the percent of ArpC2-enriched cell edge. n > 20 cells per
1530 condition.

1531 (I) Immunofluorescence images of a TRPV4 siRNA treated MEF expressing hTRPV4-eGFP.
1532 The cell was stained for phalloidin (F-actin) and anti-GFP (hTRPV4-eGFP).

1533 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
1534 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
1535 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***
1536 p < 0.005, **** p < 0.001.

1537 **Figure S3. Myosin-II and the upstream regulators of Arp2/3 are not involved in the**
1538 **control of lamellipodia protrusive activity by TRPV4. Related to Figure 3.**

1539 (A-B) Analysis of the effects of TRPV4 inhibition on phospho myosin light chain
1540 (pS19MLC2). (A) F-actin and phospho-myosin light chain (pS19MLC2) images of MEFs
1541 treated with 0.1% DMSO and TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047). (B) Average line
1542 intensity profiles of the (top) F-actin and (bottom) pS19MLC2 staining near the cell edge in
1543 the presence of DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor. $n \geq 6$ cells per condition.

1544 (C-D) Analysis of the effects of myosin II inhibition on lamellipodia protrusion speed. (C)
1545 DIC images of (left) blebbistatin-treated and (right) TRPV4 inhibitor-and-blebbistatin-co-
1546 treated MEFs. The yellow box indicates the region of the zoom-in shown on the right. (D)
1547 Quantifications of their protrusion speed. $n = 20$ cells per condition.

1548 (E-F) Localization of Abi1 in TRPV4 inhibited MEFs. (E) Fluorescent images of (top) F-actin
1549 and (bottom), labeled by eGFP-Abi1 and F-tractin-emiRFP670 respectively. (F) Average line
1550 intensity profiles of eGFP-Abi1 near the cell edge in the presence of DMSO or TRPV4
1551 inhibitor. $n = 9$ cells per condition.

1552 (G) Fluorescent phalloidin and anti-ArpC2 images of MEFs treated with non-targeting
1553 siRNA (siCtrl), TRPV4 siRNA and TRPV4 siRNA + human TRPV4-eGFP (siRNA-resistant).

1554 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
1555 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
1556 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
1557 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

1558 **Figure S4. TRPV4 does not regulate the activity of Rac1 or Cdc42. Related to Figure 4.**

1559 (A) Fluorescence images of RhoA FRET biosensor activation in MEFs expressing
1560 constitutively active (CA) or dominant negative (DN) RhoA mutant biosensors (B-E)
1561 Analyses of the effects of TRPV4 inhibition on Rac1 and Cdc42 activity by Förster
1562 Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) imaging. MEFs were transiently expressing a Rac1 or
1563 Cdc42 FRET biosensor. Fluorescence images of (B) Rac1 and (C) Cdc42 FRET biosensors
1564 activation in cells treated with 0.1% DMSO or 10 μ M HC-067047. Quantifications of the
1565 global (D) Rac1 and (E) Cdc42 FRET_{eff}. $n \geq 14$ cells per condition.

1566 (F-G) Western blot analysis of the activity of (F) Rac1 and (G) Cdc42 in MEFs treated with
1567 0.1% DMSO, TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047), or CaMKII inhibitor (10 μ M KN-93) by
1568 using the active GTPase pull-down assay.

1569 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
1570 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
1571 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
1572 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

1573 **Figure S5. Local suppression of CaMKII perturbs lamellipodia protrusion dynamics.**
1574 **Related to Figure 5.**

1575 (A) Western blot analysis of the level of phospho-CaMKII in MEFs treated with 0.1% DMSO
1576 or TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-067047). 3 isoforms of CaMKII (α , β and γ) are expressed.
1577 Vinculin was used as a loading control.

1578 (B) DIC Kymographs generated from the cells in the optogenetic CaMKII inhibition
1579 experiment. The kymographs show cell edge dynamics before and after photo-activation.
1580 The blue stripe indicates the photo-illumination period. They are extracted from cells
1581 treated (top left) without paAIP2, (top right) with paAIP2 & DMSO, or (bottom left) paAIP2
1582 & TRPV4 inhibitor.

1583 **Figure S6. Arhgef2/GEF-H1 does not regulate lamellipodial F-actin. Related to Figure**
1584 **6.**

1585 (A) Western blot analysis of VASP (a lamellipodia marker) in purified lamellipodia (LP)
1586 and cell body (CB) fractions from MEFs migrating across a 3.0- μ m pore size polycarbonate
1587 membrane. Prior to the fractionation, MEFs were treated with 0.1% DMSO, TRPV4 inhibitor
1588 (10 μ M HC-067047), or CaMKII inhibitor (10 μ M KN-93). Vimentin was used as a loading
1589 control.

1590 (B-C) Analysis of the effects of Arhgef2/GEF-H1 depletion on F-actin. (B) Fluorescent
1591 phalloidin and anti-cortactin images of MEFs treated with non-targeting siRNA (siCtrl) and
1592 Arhgef2 siRNA (siArhgef2). (C) Quantifications of lamellipodial F-actin intensity upon
1593 Arhgef2 depletion. $n = 10$ cells per condition.

1594 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments. The data are presented
1595 as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

1596 **Figure S7. Suppression of TRPV4 signaling axis reduces cell protrusive activity while**
1597 **having a minimal effect on cell-ECM interaction and cell morphology. Related to**
1598 **Figure 7.**

1599 (A-D) Cell morphological analysis of MEFs plated on a FN-coated coverslips upon TRPV4
1600 inhibition or TEM4 depletion. $n \geq 20$ cells per condition.

1601 (E-F) Analysis of the effects of TRPV4 inhibition on focal adhesions. (E) Fluorescence
1602 images of MEFs expressing paxillin-eGFP acquired by total internal reflection fluorescence
1603 (TIRF) microscopy. Cells were treated with 0.1% DMSO or TRPV4 inhibitor (10 μ M HC-
1604 067047). (F) Quantifications of (left) the total adhesive area marked by paxillin positive
1605 pixels, (middle) the average focal adhesive size, and (right) the total number of individual
1606 adhesions per cell. $n = 10$ cells per condition.

1607 (G) Quantifications of the average aspect ratio of the cell quantified from MEFs embedded
1608 in a 3D collagen matrix. $n = 10$ cells per condition.

1609 (H) Quantifications of melanoblast average mean square displacement (MSD) upon TRPV4
1610 inhibition. Melanoblast were imaged in *Mitf-Cre::Rosa26-floxed stop-TdTomato* E15.5 mouse
1611 embryo. $n \geq 74$ cells per condition.

1612 (I-J) Morphological analysis of melanoblasts (I) Quantification of melanoblast cell
1613 circularity in the presence of TRPV4 inhibitor. (J) Timelapse images of melanoblast cell
1614 expressing TdTomato in (top) control and (bottom) TRPV4 inhibition. $n \geq 74$ cells per
1615 condition.

1616 Mann-Whitney test is used for comparisons between 2 treatments and one-way ANOVA
1617 followed by Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test for comparisons between more than 2 treatments.
1618 The data are presented as mean \pm SD unless otherwise specified. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***
1619 $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure S1

Figure S2

Figure S3

Figure S4

A

Figure S5

Figure S6

Figure S7